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This SYMPOSIUM is part of the VI GRAN CANARIA INTERNATIONAL CONGRESS OF TIDES. Under the theme “GRAN CANARIA Spring Symposium on Challenges in Tourism Development: Strategies and Leadership in Tourism and Hospitality Management”, the Symposium provides an international forum for academics, researchers, professionals and students to discuss sustainability, competitiveness and economic prospects in tourism and transport.

These CONFERENCE PROCEEDINGS result from three days of knowledge and experience exchange related to Sustainable Tourism Development.

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COLLECTION OF ABSTRACTS

- 1 **The impact of motivation language on organizational performance in the tourism industry: Case of hotel companies, North of Morocco.** Kamal Loux and Anass El Ghrasli

- 2 **Sustainable Cultural Tourism Strategies. Achieving the SDGs at The Canary Museum.** Daniel Pérez Estévez

- 3 **Tourism Migrant Entrepreneurship, Enclave Strategy and Firm Performance in Crisis Times.** Antonia M. García Cabrera and María Gracia García Soto

- 4 **Navigating a food market, the internet, and the physical visit of the customer. The case study of the Mercado del Puerto of Las Palmas de Gran Canaria.** Mireya Yadranka Morgana Orellana, Sergio Moreno Gil and Tatiana David Negre

- 5 **Tourism and Sustainability: The Tourism Observatory of A Coruña.** Begoña Muíño Sar, Iria Caamaño Franco and Eduardo Guillén Solórzano

- 6 **Encouraging sustainable transport modes: a service quality of public transport to the university.** Javier Hernán Matas Monroy, Juan Carlos Martín Hernández and Concepción Román García

- 7 **Profiling Whale watching demanding behaviour. Lessons from tourist preferences in the Macaronesia Region.** Chaitanya Suárez Rojas, Yen Elizabeth Lam González, Carmelo J. León and Juan Carlos Martín

- 8 **Development and application of a Whale-watching Lexicon for the study of tourist satisfaction.** Carmelo J. León, Chaitanya Suárez Rojas, José M. Cazorla Artilles and Matías M. González Hernández

- 9 **Sustainable Preferences Values in Discrete Choice Experiment.** Jaime Blázquez Valerón, Eugenio Díaz Fariña and Carmelo J. León

- 10 **Impact of Automation on Hotel Labor: The Case of Housekeeping Staff.** Gabriela Cabello Pestano, Santiago Melián González and Jacques Bulchand Gidumal

- 11 **The Role of Information Technologies in Silver Tourism.** Jorge Fernández Tschuikin, Lorena Robaina Calderín and Lucía Melián Alzola

- 12 **Handling Negative Data in the Hotel Efficiency Sector.** Christian Hernández Guedes and Jorge V. Pérez Rodríguez

- 13 **Decomposing the Gender Wage Gap: An Analysis of the Tourism Sector at the European Level.** Marina Marfil Cotilla, Juan A. Campos Soria, M. Alecator Ribeiro and Antonio Molina García

- 14 **AI influencers in the Tourism Sector.** Carlos Cristian Díaz Santamaría, Gabriela Cabello Pestano and Jacques Bulchand Gidumal

- 15 **Is the Variable Selection Problem in Geographically Regression Model Sample-Sensitive? An Application to the Identification of price determinants for Airbnb Listings in Gran Canaria, Spain.** Rafael Suárez Vega and Dolores R. Santos Peñate

- 16 **Analysis of the Tourists' Willingness to Compensate the CO2 Emissions in the Canary Islands.** Eugenio Díaz Fariña, Aythami del Cristo Santana Padrón, Jaime Blázquez Valerón and Carmelo J. León

- 17 **Effects of Tourist Air Transportation Internalisation of CO2 Emissions in the Canary Islands.** Ana López Ojeda, Casiano Manrique de Lara Peñate and Carmelo J. León

- 18 **Perception of Airline Service Quality: Insights from User-Generated Content.** Adeim Suvanbekova and Teresa Aguiar Quintana

- 19 **Overtourism: a Demand Analysis of Tourists' Perception.** Juana M. Alonso Déniz

- 20 **Opaque Products: a Profitable Pricing Strategy for Airlines and a Popular Way of Travelling for Consumers.** Juana M. Alonso Déniz and M. Pilar Socorro Quevedo

- 21 **Volcanic Eruptions and Tourism Prosocial Consumption.** Ubay Pérez Granja, Ascensión Andina Díaz and Juan Luis Jiménez

- 22 **Satire and Social Critique in Tourism: Cartoons and Vignettes about Contemporary Tourism issues in Spanish Press.** Pedro Moreira Gregori and Francisco López del Pino

- 23 **Understanding Operational Models of Tourism Observatories.** Sara García Altmann, Raúl Hernández Martín and Hugo Padrón Ávila

- 24 **Tourist Island Destinations Vulnerability in a Multi-Hazard and Multi-risk context.** Sara García González, María García Vaquero and Noemi Padrón Fumero

- 25 **Tourist Postcards of Gran Canaria: Origins and Social Representations.** Pedro Moreira Gregori and Pablo Díaz Rodríguez
-
- 26 **Sustainable Tourism: Beyond Hospitality. A case study of EcoMarine Malta.** Patricia Patti
-
- 27 **Addressing Coordination in Tourism-Led Economies: How coordination failures can arise even when economic agents know the path to Economic growth.** Moisés Navarro Sánchez and Federico Inchausti Sintes
-
- 28 **Superyachts and Corporate Tourism: An integrated analysis.** Florin Ioras
-
- 29 **Blue Tourism: A Path Towards Sustainable Tourism Development in Blue Spaces.** Mónica M. Brito and Luís Silveira
-
- 30 **Dragon Fruit: Analysis of the potential development of Gastrotouristic products through the use of neuromarketing techniques.** Moisés Perdomo Santana and Sergio Moreno Gil
-
- 31 **Leveraging Neuromarketing and Neuroscientific approaches into persuasive Tourism Web Design and its usability: an exploration of tourists' cognitive experience enhancement.** Majid Heidari, MirFarshad Farshbafiyani Hosseini-zhad and Hojjat Emami
-
- 32 **Educational mismatch in the quality of employment in the European Tourism Sector. A Gender Perspective.** Elena Lasso de la Vega Alarcón, Juan Capo Soria and Alejandro García Pozo
-
- 33 **Social Media and Influencer Marketing in Luxury Tourism: Their Role on the Customer's Decision-Making Process.** Raúl Castro, Carlota García Pietro and Lidia Hernández López
-
- 34 **Intellectual and Emotional Responses: Neuromarketing in Botanical Gardens.** Maica Amador Marrero and Gonzalo Díaz Meneses
-
- 35 **From White Star's to White Elephants: Belfast's regeneration and rehabilitation through the Titanic.** Quarter Jonathan Skinner
-
- 36 **Technology Usage in Visitor Attractions: Leveraging Big Data from the Wi-Fi network.** Ernesto Batista Sánchez and Jim Deegan
-
- 37 **Analysis of Interdependencies in tourism: The case of Canary Island.** Andrea Rodríguez Ramos, Aythami Santana Padrón and Eugenio Díaz Fariña
-
- 38 **The Role of Water Tariffs in Water use in the hospitality industry.** Alba Estévez Bauluz, Juan José Díaz Hernández and Noemi Padrón Fumero
-
- 39 **Analysing Evolving Perceptions of Customer Satisfaction in luxury hotels.** Christian González Martel, Moamen Waleed El-Sherbiny and Teresa Aguiar Quintana
-
- 40 **Procedures for Classifying Alternatives: An application in the tourism field.** Dolores R. Santos Peñate and Rafael Suárez Vega
-
- 41 **UNESCO Creative Cities in the Inland-Centre of Portugal.** Pedro Vaz Serra and Cláudia Seabra
-
- 42 **Outbound Tourism and Economic and Social Risks: Between the Pandemic and Regional Conflicts.** Pedro Vaz Serra and Cláudia Seabra
-
- 43 **Crime Perceptions and Urban Tourism: A Systematic Literature Review.** Andreia Pereira and Claudia Seabra
-
- 44 **The Uneven way to renewables deployment: Specificities of island destinations.** Yen Lam González and Matías González Hernández
-
- 45 **Critical Success Factors of Wine Tourism Regions.** Mylona Meletia, Mamalis Spyridon, Emmanouloudis Dimitrios and Arseniou Spyridon
-
- 46 **The behaviour of the new gamer consumer when faced with the advertising placement of fashion brands in videogames.** Maica Amador Marrero and Gonzalo Díaz Meneses
-
- 47 **Impact of Sustainability on Tourist Satisfaction in Rural and Urban Areas in Spain From Online Reviews.** María Fernanda Bernal Salazar, Elisa Baraibar Diez and Jesús Collado Agudo

Abstract 1

The impact of motivation language on organizational performance in the tourism industry: Case of hotel companies, North of Morocco.

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KEYWORDS: Motivation, performance, work, tourism, employees.

ABSTRACT: The work of leaders in all organizations relies heavily on oral language practiced in the workplace, particularly how superiors use that language to communicate with their employees (Conger, 1991). As a result, the verbal language of managers or supervisors represents up to 82% of their working time which includes communicating objectives to subordinates, clarifying standards as well as evaluating staff performance (Yukl, 2002). "Managing is speaking" refers to the ontological capacity of language to structure the actions of individuals in the context of perceived realities (King, 2003). Leaders communicate both verbally and through their actions and behaviors (Sarros, et al., 2014). Several studies, in this sense, have highlighted the importance of oral communication skills of the leader or superior to obtain good results (Graen, et al., 1986; Robbins, 1993).

This paper explores the relationship between "motivational language theory" of Sullivan (1988) and job performance in the tourism industry. The superior's use of a motivational language (including (1) perlocutionary or direction-giving, (2) illocutionary or sharing feelings, and (3) locutionary or explaining culture) would positively influence the job performance in its dimensions (task performance and the contextual performance). The founded results, thanks to the structural equation modeling on a sample of 132 employees from the region of Tangier Tetouen Al Hoceima (north of Morocco), confirm, in large part, the positive impact of motivating language on the individual job performance. More specifically, empathetic language and a lesser degree directive language have a positive and significant impact on both dimensions of job performance. On the other hand, the meaning-creating language justifies weakly the contextual performance and does not influence the task performance.

The survey was carried out using a questionnaire administered to employees of the three touristic franchises used in our empirical approach. As recommended by Blais & al. (2009), the focus group is useful before a survey to pre-test the questionnaire and to understand the dynamics in which the survey subjects are placed. This exploratory phase also proved necessary to approach the notions of motivating language and work performance in relation to the particularities of the companies targeted by our empirical approach.

Data was collected via an online questionnaire. 143 questionnaires were returned out of 180. 11 were rejected due to missing data, leaving 132 questionnaires used in the present research.

Abstract 2

Sustainable Cultural Tourism Strategies. Achieving the SDGs at The Canary Museum.

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KEYWORDS: Tourism, Sustainability, Strategy, Culture, Museums.

ABSTRACT: Cultural tourism and sustainable development are intrinsically linked. Culture contributes to sustainability by its very nature, since it preserves heritage and raises awareness among the population. Museums are a fundamental pillar in cultural tourism, and they play an essential role in sustainability promotion at an environmental, social and governance level, since they have evolved from being a place to visit to becoming an institution to transform the society. In this work, we propose measures to implement the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) by integrating sustainability as a key policy in the museum strategy.

El Museo Canario (The Canary Museum) is the institution that preserves, researches and disseminates the historical and cultural heritage of the Canary Islands since 1879. Every year, thousands of tourists visit its facilities, making it a leading cultural destination in the Canary Islands. Sustainability is integrated as a main pillar into the Museum's strategy and activities.

Culture is a vector for sustainability, as recognised in the international frameworks as UNESCO Convention (1972), the Freiburg Convention (IIEDH 2007) and the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development (ONU 2015) and at a regional level in the Canary Islands 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development (GOBCAN 2021).

Museums are agents for social change and development (Nascimento, 2008), and need strategies to promote the implementation of the Sustainable Development Goals (Hansson 2022, Ásványi and Fehér 2023). The current definition of 'museum' enhances these institutions to promote diversity and sustainability (ICOM, 2022).

The methodology applied on this paper consists of an Importance/Performance Analysis (IPA Analysis) which has been developed from surveys filled by visitors, where they identify the relevance on sustainable variables in museums which are compared to their real perception during their experience at The Canary Museum. The Importance/Performance analysis has high potential for evaluating the effectiveness of organizations in adapting to public preferences (Pérez 2015, Kucukusta et al. 2013, Youjae and Gong 2013, Ziegler et al. 2012, Deng et al. 2008, Zhang and Chow 2004). This methodology allows to detect the degree of adaptation of its activity to the expectations.

Results show the level of adequacy of the Museum's behaviour on sustainability values to the priorities of the visitors. The analysis shows four areas depending on the level of accuracy in the Museum's response to tourist preferences and perception. There can be seen relevant and non-relevant sustainability areas, which are covered in efficient or non-efficient ways.

This paper also outlines the most recent trends in the strategic management of the Sustainable Development Goals in tourism, presents a proposal for their specific application on the cultural tourism industry, and evaluates the implementation of the SDGs at The Canary Museum. Special attention is paid to analyze how museums can contribute to sustainability by studying the preferences of tourists based on their expectations and evaluating its impact.

Abstract 3

Tourism Migrant Entrepreneurship, Enclave Strategy and Firm Performance in Crisis Times.

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KEYWORDS: Immigrant entrepreneurship, enclave strategy, institutional theory, social resources, business performance, times of crisis.

ABSTRACT: Considering immigrant entrepreneurs in the tourism industry, this paper examines macro- and meso- level antecedents of their decisions concerning the use of enclave strategy for their tourism businesses in their countries of residence, and how the use of such strategy relates to firm performance in the face of an economic crisis. To this respect, the enclave strategy can be conceptualised as the choice by the immigrant entrepreneur of a product/market scope that involves a value chain dominated by compatriots (e.g., suppliers, customer, employees, partnerships), and which is independent of the venture location, that is, whether ventures are “geographically clustered” in ethnic enclaves or located in the mainstream market.

Thus, this work contributes to literature on tourism entrepreneurship by immigrants in four ways: (1) by discussing the use of the enclave strategy for their tourism ventures started up in their countries of residence; (2) by exploring whether immigrants connections with compatriots and local residents (meso-level variable) condition the use of the enclave strategy; (3) by exploring whether institutions in immigrants’ countries of origin (macro-level variable) condition their strategic decisions concerning the use of enclave strategy; and (4) by exploring enclave strategy as a potential vehicle for sustaining tourism firm performance in times of crisis.

To test the hypothesis, we use a sample of 159 immigrant entrepreneurs settled in Spain who have started up a tourism SME in the third most important tourism destination in that country (i.e., the Canary Islands). We collected individual- and meso- level data from a survey and macro-level variables from secondary databases (i.e., Work Competitiveness Yearbook). The survey was conducted in 2011 (March 20th to April 20 th), right in the middle of the 2008–2014 Spanish financial crisis, also known as the Great Spanish Depression.

Concerning results, firstly, we found two different dimensions of the enclave strategy: ‘supply sources/product offered’ and ‘target market’. While 43.7% of the tourism firms sampled implemented just one dimension of the strategy, 23.8% adopted both, and 32.5% neither of them. Secondly, and referring meso-level variables, the more connections immigrant entrepreneurs have with compatriots, the more the enclave strategy will be used in both its dimensions. Thirdly, and regarding macro-level variables, results show that the more the institutions in the immigrant’s home country facilitate business activities and competitiveness, the greater will be the use of the two dimensions of the enclave strategy. Finally, if compared to businesses that do not use any dimension of the enclave strategy, those that use one or both achieve higher performance in times of crisis.

Abstract 4

Navigating a food market, the internet, and the physical visit of the customer. The case study of the Mercado del Puerto of Las Palmas de Gran Canaria.

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KEYWORDS: Visual attention, navigation, eye tracking, web design.

ABSTRACT: This research studies the consumer experience in a market from two perspectives. On the one hand, it examines the customer behaviour while browsing the website. On the other, it analyses the customer behaviour in the natural environment by understanding the on-site visit experience. This research used eye movement analysis through the eye tracking technique and self-reports to obtain information regarding users' experiences and attention patterns of participants while browsing a web page or through their movement flow in person in the market.

The first experiment was conducted with a screen-based eye tracking, for which two tasks were projected to different participants related to the web navigation of the market webpage. Task one involved purchasing on the website, and Task two focused on subscribing to the newsletter. A total of 12 participants (five women and seven men, with an average age of 40) were included. The second experiment (on-site) asked the participants to find a specific food stall using a physical market map. A total of 10 participants (five women and five men, with an average age of 47) took part in this experiment; the eye-tracking data were collected using wearable eye-tracking Glasses. Both experiments were analysed to understand user behaviour and attention patterns in different contexts, providing valuable insights into web usability and onsite navigation in a market environment.

The results of experiment one indicated that participants faced challenges in finding the online shopping page or locating the subscription banner within the indicated period, resulting in a low success rate and a high level of frustration. In task one, there was a notable increase in the number of fixations on the home bar, with greater attention directed to the jobs section. In task two, attention was focused on the Home and History section while searching for the newsletter. Overall, the results underline the importance of well-structured and organised web pages to facilitate effective navigation and customer satisfaction.

Finally, with the eye tracking experiment in experiment two, related to the flow of movement, it was found that participants generally paid more attention to specific stalls and made a general tour of the entire map. Those who found the correct stall demonstrated a wider visual path than those who did not. Participants often initially followed a straight line and then decided where to turn or ask for directions. These findings contribute to a better understanding of user experiences in these specific scenarios.

These preliminary results highlight participants' challenges in both web browsing and onsite physical navigation tasks, emphasising the need for easy-to-use interfaces and clear navigation cues on websites and in physical environments such as markets. Participants' gaze patterns and navigation choices provide valuable information about user behaviour in these contexts.

Abstract 5

Tourism and Sustainability: The Tourism Observatory of A Coruña.

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KEYWORDS: Tourism Observatory, intelligent management, intelligent planning and sustainable indicators.

The success of tourism development derives from the proper collection and interpretation of up-to-date statistics. To this end, the establishment of an Observatory allows for the acquisition of this data and also serves as a simulation tool to predict different scenarios and levels of sustainability. Numerous factors affect tourism planning, making it incomprehensible today without tourism intelligence and Big Data. Ivars and Vera (2019) identify smart infrastructures as key elements for achieving sustainable development goals. In this context, a green destination will merge with technological futurism, involving new data sources (big data).

Against this backdrop, this communication aims to present the challenges that a Tourism Observatory might face for territorial sustainability. The case study will focus on the Tourism Observatory of A Coruña (OTC), sharing the initial experience of its implementation during 2023. This project, launched thanks to a collaboration agreement between the City Council, through its Tourism and Congress Consortium, and the University of A Coruña, provides a unique character to the integration of academia in its configuration, particularly in its coordination and function. The main objective of this project is to design and provide a tourism intelligence tool that allows for the stable collection and analysis of relevant destination data. In its first year of operation, the OTC has become an essential tool for tourism planning and management because it enables and facilitates the structuring and analysis of this vast amount of information, as well as predicting and anticipating possible trends and needs. Additionally, it allows for the diagnosis of the sector through the collection of two main indicators and results associated with the evolution of two different pillars/products of the destination.

This communication will focus on the process of selecting sustainable indicators and integrating them into the destination's tourism strategy, as well as their influence on adopted public policies. Regarding the definition of indicators, all potential indicators identified were examined based on the availability and reliability of the source, and through a consultative process, the final indicators for analysis were defined.

Abstract 6

Encouraging sustainable transport modes: a service quality of public transport to the university.

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KEYWORDS: University, transport, students, discrete choice model, Best-Worst scales, Importance-Performance Analysis.

ABSTRACT: One of the most important objectives of governments is incentivizing the use of sustainable transport modes, such as the public transport. There are many reasons that support this idea, for instance, the reduction in CO2 emissions or decreasing the congestion on the roads. Moreover, this transport mode is highly used by students to access to their respective university campus.

The objective of this study is to analyze the service quality of public transport to the different university campus located in Gran Canaria. To do that, an importance-satisfaction analysis based on the use of Best-Worst scales was carried out. This method allows to know the degree of importance and satisfaction with respect to the main attributes that influence the service. Additionally, it is framed into the Random Utility Theory, that was developed by McFadden (1974).

Analyzing students' preferences regarding transport mode choice has been studied in the literature. Some results indicate that this population segment prefers direct alternatives over those involving interchange during PT travel (Yen et al., 2017) and also places a lower value on travel time savings than adult commuters but a higher value than senior citizens (Agarwal et al., 2020). Additionally, the ways to encourage the use of sustainable transport modes such as bicycles (Migliore et al., 2021; Orozco-Fontalvo et al., 2018; Ribeiro & Fonseca, 2022; Torrisi et al., 2021) and transport-sharing systems and car-pooling (Bruglieri et al., 2011; Lue & Colorni, 2009); Rotaris et al., 2019) have also been object of analysis. Furthermore, studying which factors are crucial in quality perception of the service. In this sense, some factors such as frequency, speed, punctuality, proximity, safety, fare, comfort in the bus and information available about the service have been highlighted (De Oña et al., 2012; Mulley et al., 2017). Finally, some measures that can improve and encourage public transport use among university students can be summarized in expanding and optimising the network of bus (Gundlach et al., 2018), increasing service frequency and reducing waiting times (González et al., 2015) or establishing direct bus routes to and from university campuses (Sanko, 2020).

A questionnaire was sent to the university students by e-mail, and it contained questions related with the characteristics of the travel by public transport, the Best-Worst experiment, a Likert-scale valuation and, finally, some socio-economic questions.

The main results suggest that the factors that require policy intervention are the bus frequency, the punctuality in keeping services to schedules, and the availability of a direct service to the campus. The importance of this research is to provide helpful information that can be used by public transport managers to implement successful strategies that improve the level of service, increase the satisfaction of current users and attract new users.

Abstract 7

Profiling Whale-watching demanding behaviour. Lessons from tourist preferences in the Macaronesia Region.

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KEYWORDS: Whale-watching, tourists' motivations, fuzzy logic, Triangular fuzzy numbers, Fuzzy-Hybrid TOPSIS.

ABSTRACT: The commercial whaling ban was implemented in the 1980s because many whale species were endangered or vulnerable to extinction. The International Whaling Commission (IWC) has a moratorium on commercial whaling that has been in place since 1986. However, some countries, such as Norway and Japan, continue to defy the moratorium and hunt whales. Besides, commercial whaling was no longer perceived as economically viable because significant negative externalities were not considered in marine ecosystem preservation. For example, whales eat large amounts of krill and other small fish, which helps to control populations of these prey species. Whales also defecate iron-rich faeces that fertilise phytoplankton, which is the base of the marine food chain. Additionally, social, ethical and moral norms consider that commercial whaling is inhumane because whales are highly intelligent and social animals that experience pain and suffering just like any other mammal. Thus, whale-watching has become the most important economic activity involving whales worldwide.

In fact, whale-watching has become popular in recent years, and for good reasons. It is a unique and rewarding experience to see these magnificent creatures in their natural habitat. Nevertheless, it is necessary to develop whale-watching products that satisfy tourists' expectations with the lowest environmental pressure/impact and harassment on cetaceans' wellbeing. To this end, the study is based on a 19-item scale extracted from previous studies describing the characteristics of the experience, such as seeing whales up close, feeling safe or learning opportunities. A Fuzzy-Hybrid TOPSIS method is used to analyse whale watchers' demanding and undemanding behaviour through a synthetic indicator. A convenience sample of 490 tourists visiting the main six islands of the Macaronesia archipelago, namely Gran Canaria and Tenerife (the Canary Islands), Madeira, and Faial, Pico and San Miguel (the Azores), is used. Our results show that the synthetic index is affected by island, main motivation, group typology, group size, belonging to a natural association, household income and expenditure per night. Interesting insights for policymakers, whale-watching service companies and destination marketing organisations are finally discussed.

Abstract 8

Development and application of a Whale-watching Lexicon for the study of tourist satisfaction.

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KEYWORDS: Whale watching, lexicon, satisfaction, TripAdvisor.

ABSTRACT: Whale-watching tourism is nowadays one of the most popular wildlife-based tourism activities, as demonstrated by the more than 15 million tourists who carry out the activity annually. However, it also impacts the well-being of the cetaceans. In this regard, understanding consumer behaviour is paramount for addressing the sustainable management of the activity, especially nowadays, where communication platforms and networks allow customers to voice their opinions quickly and easily. The opinion of one user is considered trustworthy to others, influencing the latter expectations and travel decisions. This situation increases the demand for high-quality and tailored experiences, hindering tourist satisfaction performance and responsible activity management.

This study explores the underpinnings of consumer-stated opinions and satisfaction with whale-watching tours by analysing data from social media platforms. In particular, the present work utilised data from 2,313 whale-watching tours announced on TripAdvisor - one of the travel industry's most important community-based review platforms. A new lexicon for whale-watching tourism was built up from the analysis of the 96,806 reviews posted on TripAdvisor about the tours' experiences and a complimentary review of the existing literature in the field. After data pre-processing and expert validation, the final lexicon comprised 1,554 words distributed into four main categories and 24 subcategories. The categories account for i) the physical and human capital (e.g., booking planning, boat features, crew and staff, onboard safety equipment), ii) environmental resources (e.g., cetaceans' behaviour, other wildlife, photo opportunity, climate and sea conditions), iii) the experiential and operational aspects describing the tour (e.g., navigation, track and approach, passive/active observation, booking planning, tour cancellation), iv) consumers' perceived value of the experience (e.g., concerning crowdedness) and v) individuals' sustainability concerns (e.g., responsible behaviour, wildlife protection and conservation, technological innovation).

By conducting ordered probit models, the consistency and suitability of the new lexicon were positively tested. Findings also show the salient aspects of tourist satisfaction, including their feelings and concerns about the tour development. This is critical for responsible whale-watching management and wildlife conservation in the long run. In other words, this study contributes two-fold to research in whale-watching tourism. On the one hand, it provides a new tool for assessing consumer opinions from social media platforms, which lets the researcher generate information from these opinions and track tendencies of tourism demands in real time. On the other hand, a worldwide picture of whale-watchers of the last thirteen years is represented, showing consumer interests, feelings, and concerns.

Abstract 9

Sustainable Preferences Values in Discrete Choice Experiment.

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KEYWORDS: Sustainable Tourism, Discrete Choice Experiments (DCE), Willingness to Pay (WTP), Meta-regression Analysis (MRA), Sustainability Attributes.

ABSTRACT: Sustainable tourism has gained significant interest, but more cohesive research knowledge on tourists' willingness to pay (WTP) is needed. This investigation provides a unique and comprehensive synthesis of tourists' WTP for sustainable attributes. This article weaves the conceptual foundations of tourism with the social and natural sciences, constituting a crucial path toward a more nuanced understanding of sustainable tourism. This study conducts a systematic review and meta-regression analysis to synthesize evidence on marginal willingness to pay for sustainable attributes based on 47 discrete choice (DCE) papers. The findings reveal that tourists are more inclined to pay for sustainable product features related to nature, the environment, and local communities. The study also delves into tourism practices and highlights possible ways to mitigate the impact on daily life in tourist areas.

WTP estimates increase with more attributes and larger samples, while payment vehicles and sustainability status of attributes significantly influence willingness to pay. These findings provide novel evidence to guide research design and highlight sustainable features that align with tourists' preferences. This meta-regression equips tourism academics and professionals with crucial knowledge to promote sustainability by incorporating it into offerings with demonstrated consumer value. Furthermore, this work advocates for methodological standardization in DCE studies within sustainable tourism, a step towards enhancing the comparability and reliability of research outcomes. As the constantly evolving nature of tourism demands a re-evaluation of existing paradigms, this timely meta-regression offers novel approaches, concepts, and frameworks to drive new research, models, and practices.

Abstract 10

Impact of Automation on Hotel Labor: The Case of Housekeeping Staff.

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KEYWORDS: Technological change, automation Impact, routine tasks.

ABSTRACT: Since the Industrial Revolution, technology has led to the disappearance of many occupations while simultaneously creating new ones. Historically, these changes have facilitated the reassignment of the workforce to new roles and activities. However, technological change is now occurring at an increasingly rapid and intense pace. Advances in artificial intelligence (AI), specifically in machine learning and deep learning, have begun to impact tasks and positions that were once considered immune to automation, particularly within the service sector.

Numerous studies have attempted to determine the impact of automation on employment. In recent years, different conceptual frameworks have been designed to explain this impact, constructing models that categorize occupations based on five dimensions that reflect the nature of the work involved: routine cognitive, routine manual, non-routine cognitive analytical, non-routine cognitive interpersonal, and non-routine manual (Autor et al., 2003). Other research has developed indices, such as the routine task intensity index (RTI), with the objective of gauging the degree of routine characterizing occupations (Långstedt, 2021). The foundational hypothesis underpinning these propositions posits that technology automates routine tasks while concurrently complementing human workers in non-routine endeavors.

However, existing research has some limitations. Firstly, by focusing on the professional occupation without delving into the tasks that constitute it, they assume that all tasks have the same degree of routine. This limitation is acknowledged by the studies themselves. Secondly, as a result of this assumption, they overlook the fact that different tasks within a position may require varying total working hours from the employee. Consequently, an occupation may have a high percentage of highly automatable tasks, occupying a small part of the working day, while the remaining tasks, which are difficult to automate, consume the rest of the working time.

This study aims to go beyond these limitations by conducting a more detailed analysis of the tasks that constitute a specific professional occupation. The selected occupation for this purpose is "housekeeping staff," which typically employs the largest number of workers within hotel staff. Thus, based on the prevailing hypothesis regarding the possibility of job automation, the analysis will determine the degree of automation of the most representative position in hotel activities. Hotels with a minimum of three stars and a minimum of 50 rooms have been selected for this purpose. Among them, special attention is given to establishments offering sun and beach amenities, which are most representative of the Canary Islands. This will be the geographical area where the research will take place.

The ongoing research aims to address the following questions: What tasks are carried out in the position of housekeeping staff? What is the significance of each task in this occupation?

To what extent are these tasks characterized by routine? What degree of routine defines the housekeeping staff occupation?

Answering these questions will enable the determination of the level of automation associated with the housekeeping staff position.

Abstract 11

The Role of Information Technologies in Silver Tourism.

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KEYWORDS: Silver economy, ict, tourism.

ABSTRACT: The global population is aging as a result of longer life expectancy and fewer births. According to forecasts, by 2050 almost half of the population will be over 65 years of age. The literature extends this age range to the point of recognizing as the silver population all individuals over 50 years of age, who are included in what is called the “silver population”. The silver population has important socio-economic implications, significantly affecting the management of companies and sectors, from the approach to the customer to the hiring of workers with what has come to be known as intergenerational integration. It is a new framework for action that gives rise to a new economy of opportunities, the so-called “Silver Economy”. The rapid advance of Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs) coincides with this phenomenon, raising questions about possible digital divides and technological opportunities in the Silver Economy.

The aim of the paper is examine the role of ICTs in Silver Tourism. To outline the framework of the study, the existing literature on the relationship between ICTs and the Silver Economy is analysed, using bibliometric analysis through VOSviewer. This software is a content analysis tool for the construction and visualization of bibliometric networks, known as “scientific mapping”. This approach is divided into two phases, with a sequential logic. After an initial review of scientific articles working on the topic of study, the search descriptors that best describe the topics analyzed were selected. Subsequently, three searches were conducted in relevant scientific databases, such as Web of Science and Scopus, to generate the necessary databases. The collected articles were subjected to a filtering process, eliminating duplicates and thus refining a consolidated database. Finally, VOSViewer was used to perform a bibliometric analysis, allowing the visualization and study of thematic patterns and trends present in the collected literature.

Results reveal the importance of ICTs as a strategic and operational cornerstone for the development of the Silver Economy. It is recognized that the older population requires products and services adapted to their needs, with ICTs being both a driver and a barrier to the development of this new economic scenario. Based on the above, we proceeded to evaluate the participation of publications related to the field of tourism and to review articles analyzing the relationships, effects and consequences of ICTs in the field of tourism and silver tourists. As a result, an important gap was identified and future avenues for research on the role of ICTs in the design of tourism offerings, the quality and value of services at any stage of the experience, as well as the evaluation of these services, focused on the silver market of the tourism sector (Silver Tourism), are proposed.

Abstract 12

Handling Negative Data in the Hotel Efficiency Sector.

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KEYWORDS: Efficiency, hotels, determinants.

ABSTRACT: The efficiency of an unbalanced panel of Spanish hotels for the period 1997-2021 is analysed in this paper considering the presence of an output which can adopt negative values (Earnings Before Interest, Taxes, Depreciation, and Amortization; EBITDA). To do so, we apply the Range Directional Model (Portela et al., 2004) and the modified super-efficiency Range Directional Model (Hatami-Marbini et al., 2018), which the latter obtaining a complete ranking of the hotels. These are non-parametric approaches that departure from traditional DEA method and allow one to consider non-positive inputs/outputs. A truncated Bayesian Tobit regression is applied in a second stage to analyse the effect of a set of determinant variables on the efficiency obtained by hotels. In overall terms, average efficiency is high in all Spanish regions, which could be explained due to its maturity as a destination. However, important differences are found. For instance, hotels located in the Canary Islands obtained the lowest efficiency scores, whereas hotels placed in the Valencian Community achieved the highest efficiency measures. On the other hand, despite being the most important Spanish region in terms of tourist arrivals, Catalan hotels only outperform Canarian hotels. Analysis of determinant factors also show important differences between Spanish regions, with differentiation factors (e.g., golf course or adult-only hotel) and supply characteristics (e.g., labour productivity or hotel chain) being among the most important variables in explaining hotels' efficiencies. For example, adult-only hotels obtained higher efficiency scores than familiar hotels in Andalusia, the Canary Islands and Catalonia. Labour productivity has a positive effect on efficiency in all regions, justifying the adoption of measures oriented to increase labour skills. Furthermore, category shows a negative effect on the efficiency achieved by Canarian hotels, as 3-star hotels outperform 4-star, 5-star, and 5-star Great Luxury hotels. However, in the Balearic Islands or Catalonia, category is positively associated with efficiency. Results found here show that policies adopted recently by Balearic institutions has effectively shift its tourism demand towards a high purchase power kind of tourism, while Canarian infrastructure continues being mainly oriented towards a traditional sun and sand kind of tourism. In fact, in the Canary Islands, hotels located in Tenerife obtained higher efficiency scores than hotels placed in Lanzarote and Gran Canaria. Hoteliers located in these islands should increase their efficiency trying to attract a type of tourism with a higher purchase power. To do so, they could focus on renovating their tourism infrastructure.

Results found in this paper are relevant in several aspects. From an empirical perspective, this is the first time a negative output has been considered in the analysis of hotel efficiency. Furthermore, literature applying super-efficiency approaches to deal with hotel efficiency is scarce. From a practical perspective, analysing the determinant factors of efficiency from a regional perspective is especially interesting for hoteliers and policymakers.

Abstract 13

Decomposing the Gender Wage Gap: An Analysis of the Tourism Sector at the European Level.

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KEYWORDS: Gender wage gap, Discriminatory component, Hierarchical linear models, Country heterogeneity, European countries, Tourism.

ABSTRACT: Statement of the research question: Studies carried out in different countries show that workers in the tourism sector face unfavourable labour and pay conditions and a significant gender wage gap, which shows that this is an international phenomenon. However, this matter has only been studied at national level in specific countries, such as Spain, the United Kingdom, Norway, Portugal, or Brazil, among others (Burgess, 2003; Dashper, 2019; Guimarães and Silva, 2016; Santos and Varejão, 2007; Skalpe, 2007; Santero, Segovia, Castro, Figueroa and Talón, 2015; Oliver and Sard, 2020; Thrane, 2008). However, to our knowledge, no international comparisons have been carried out to explain the heterogeneity of the gender wage gap across countries and its main determinants. We have not found any studies that analyse what part of this cross-country heterogeneity could be explained by the contextual, economic, and institutional conditions of each country, as well as by factors that particularly affect the tourism sector at the international level, such as educational mismatch, labour mobility or occupational segregation, among others.

Objective: This paper uses a micro and macro perspectives simultaneously, through a multilevel approach, which may be helpful for understanding how the characteristics of the employees of each country and how the country characteristics can affect the differences at European level in the gender wage gap and its discriminatory component in the tourism sector.

Data: We created a combined dataset, based on the latest EU Structure Earnings Survey (SES- 2018), that contains matched employer-employee data in the EU-28 countries, with country-level contextual variables obtained from other international statistical sources.

Methodology: Due to the hierarchical structure of the matched employee-employer data in the SES database, a multilevel analysis is proposed to carry out an estimation of the gender wage gap for international comparability across EU-28 countries. For the application of this hierarchical model, a two-level random intercept model is considered because workers (first level) are grouped into countries (second level), so the error term can be decomposed into differences between countries, and between individuals within each country. This method allows us to analyse the contribution of individual determinants (worker, job, and establishment characteristics), as well as the contribution of contextual determinants (with a special interest in institutional, regulatory, and labour market factors) to explain the discriminatory and non- discriminatory components of the gender wage gap in the tourism sector.

Results: A general finding from the analyses indicated that significant variance exists within and among nations in wage structures. The results also show that heterogeneity between countries explained by contextual factors, such as the economic and institutional conditions of the European countries, are key factors for decomposing the gender wage gap in the tourism sector, although, individual heterogeneity due to educational mismatch, labour mobility or occupational segregation, among others, are also relevant.

Abstract 14

AI influencers in the Tourism Sector.

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KEYWORDS: Generative AI, virtual influencers, tourism sector.

ABSTRACT: Artificial Intelligence (AI) is reaching all business sectors of the economy. Numerous scientific articles have recently analyzed its real effects, both positive and negative. One of the fields that has recently generated the most interest is Generative Artificial Intelligence (GAI), understood as systems that generate content of all kinds: text, images, video, etc. GAI is usually based on the so-called LLM (large language models), among which we mention ChatGPT (OpenAI), LLaMa (Meta) and LaMDA (Google). In turn, these models have given rise to tools such as ChatGPT and Bard for text, and Dall-e, Midjourney and Stable Diffusion for images. As the models have progressed, content generation has significantly improved. Recently, the ability to generate realistic images has begun to be provided.

On the other hand, the figure of the influencer has existed in the tourism sector for several years. These are people who are able to influence other's decisions through their activities on social networks. Influencers generate relevant and attractive content, which allows them to connect with an audience that sees what the influencer presents which in turn impacts their decisions. For example, in the field of tourism, in the process of choosing a destination, a hotel or an activity. Usually, a person is considered an influencer when their followers are at least in the range of tens of thousands.

In recent years, a new trend has emerged: computer-generated influencers or computergenerated imagery (CGI) influencers, also known as AI influencers and as virtual influencers. These are virtual characters that are created through images generated by a computer and that can be used to promote a tourist product or to participate in the creation of immersive virtual experiences. Typically, these influencers identify themselves in their profiles as AI-generated. The images they post are so realistic that, if they did not identify themselves as such, it could seem they are real people. One of the most representative examples of these influencers is Miquela (@lilmiquela) who has approximately 3 million followers. In the tourism sector, those with the largest amount of followers are currently in the ranges of hundreds of thousands.

Our research will focus on analyzing the AI influencers that currently exist in the tourism sector, comparing them with human influencers and observing the behavior that the former have on social networks. To do this, among other things, we will analyze what type of publications they make, the impact they have, the number and type of followers they have, as well as which ones generate the greatest connection with customers.

In short, we will analyze whether there are differences between AI influencers and human influencers and the current and potential value that AI influencers are contributing and could contribute to the tourism sector. As a result of the analysis, recommendations will be made for tourism companies focusing on whether it is interesting to use GAI for the types of purposes human influencers are usually employed and what impact its application could have on the tourism sector.

Abstract 15

Is the Variable Selection Problem in Geographically Regression Model Sample-Sensitive? An Application to the Identification of price determinants for Airbnb Listings in Gran Canaria, Spain.

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KEYWORDS: Model selection, GWR, dimension reduction, heuristic algorithms, spatial sampling.

ABSTRACT: The Geographically Weighted Regression (GWR) has been shown to be a very powerful tool for describing phenomena in which the factors that determine them do not affect the entire study space homogeneously. The computational effort required by these models makes their application to large samples very complicated since it involves estimating the coefficients for each of the locations in the sample. Prior to model estimation, the bandwidth, i.e., the area of influence for each sample unit, would have to be determined, which normally takes longer than the GWR estimation itself. On the other hand, the problem of selecting the variables that best fit a regression is complex when the number of candidates for explanatory variables is high due to the large number of alternatives that should be considered. Therefore, the problem of selecting the variables that best fit a GWR model turns out to be of very high computational complexity when the number of houses and/or the amount of candidate factors to be explanatory variables is high.

The main objective of this paper is to test whether the problem of finding the best-fitting GWR model when the problem size is large can be solved with small samples that allow it to be solved in reasonable time. In particular, we analyse the problem of selecting the factors that best adjust the rental prices of Airbnb properties in Gran Canaria (Spain) by means of a GWR model. The dataset used contains the 2238 complete houses, discarding private or shared rooms, offered on the portal in January 2018 in Gran Canaria. And, as possible determinants, 41 variables describing characteristics of the listings, its environment or its host are considered. The problem was solved using three sample sizes, two sampling methods and three selection procedures. Among the deductions obtained, we observe that the results for small samples (around 11% of the population) are significantly worse than those obtained for medium (23%) or large samples (45.25%). Moreover, when samples are small, spatial sampling (considering the spatial distribution of listings) obtains better results than simple random sampling. However, when the sample size increases the differences are no longer significant. Finally, a classification algorithm is applied based on the frequency with which the variables appear in the models. As a general rule, the variables chosen can be classified into three groups, one with variables that appear almost always, around 90-100% of the instances, another containing variables that appear around 50%, and a final group of disposable variables whose frequency is very low.

Abstract 16

Analysis of the Tourists' Willingness to Compensate the CO2 Emissions in the Canary Islands.

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KEYWORDS: Carbon offsetting; voluntarism; sustainable tourism; willingness to pay; Bayesian Model Averaging.

ABSTRACT: Tourism is a major sector contributing significantly to global warming, with an estimated 8% of global CO2 emissions attributable to tourism. The majority of these emissions are linked to the aviation sector, accounting for nearly 90%. However, the environmental impact of tourism extends beyond air travel, encompassing the services consumed at destinations, which have a profound effect on both local communities and environmental systems.

Since the early 2000s, voluntary carbon offset mechanisms have been promoted as a measure to reduce the carbon footprint of tourism. The most well-known example involves air travel, where tourists can pay an additional amount to offset the CO2 emissions generated by their flights. Nevertheless, the efficacy of these mechanisms is questioned due to issues such as the methodologies used to calculate carbon emissions, the projects funded by offsets, the prices set, and the transparency of the process.

Our study evaluates the potential effectiveness of a voluntary carbon offset mechanism for tourists visiting the Canary Islands. Utilizing data published by the Canary Islands Institute of Statistics (ISTAC), which includes responses from nearly 80,000 tourists interviewed in 2022 and 2023, we analyze the determinants influencing tourists' willingness to offset the emissions generated during their vacations.

The analysis reveals a higher probability of carbon offset participation among tourists attracted to the Canary Islands for their cultural heritage, authenticity, quality of hiking trails, and environmental appeal. This likelihood also increases for tourists visiting the green islands (La Palma, El Hierro, and La Gomera), those staying in rural hotels and campsites, and those engaging in active tourism activities such as water sports, cycling, running, and nature activities, while immersing themselves in the local culture. Demographically, women, tourists with high economic and educational levels, and residents of Germany, Switzerland, Ireland, and the Netherlands show a higher propensity to offset their carbon emissions.

Conversely, tourists drawn to the Canary Islands for sun and beach tourism, commercial offerings, nightlife, and low prices are less inclined to participate in carbon offsetting. This trend is also evident among tourists visiting the more congested islands (Gran Canaria and Tenerife), those opting for all-inclusive services, and last-minute tourists who plan their trips within less than a day.

Based on these findings, we conclude that a hypothetical voluntary carbon offset mechanism for tourists at the destination is likely to fail. This conclusion is rooted in the principle of "polluter pays," which is not upheld under voluntary mechanisms. Tourists whose activities and services consumed have the highest environmental impact are the least willing to voluntarily offset their emissions. Therefore, to address the shortcomings of voluntary mechanisms, we suggest implementing an environmental tax on tourism services to internalize the negative externalities of tourism activities.

Abstract 17

Effects of Tourist Air Transportation Internalisation of CO₂ Emissions in the Canary Islands.

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KEYWORDS: Tourism, emissions, Canary Islands

ABSTRACT: Tourism has become one of the world's leading economic activities, growing from 3.26% of global GDP in 2010 to 4.1% in 2019. However, this development and its contribution to the economy has been accompanied by other negative socio-environmental impacts. Tourism growth has been possible thanks to technological improvements that have facilitated connections between different parts of the world and access by tourists. Nevertheless, many of the negative impacts of tourism are also due to the use of these transport modes and their contribution to air pollution. Impacts related with air transport become more relevant on islands, where tourist can only arrive by airplane. In this paper, we calculate the impact of the internalization of the emissions generated by tourists who travelled by plane to the Canary Islands in the period 2010-2021.

By employing the ICAO-CEM model, we compute the emissions produced by individual aircraft, taking into account the aircraft type, origin country, and destination island. As it was expected, tourists from the United Kingdom and Germany exhibit the highest level of emissions during the examined timeframe. This is due to the fact that these nationalities constitute the predominant portion of visitors who visit the Canary Islands, with Nordics following closely behind. Nevertheless, when examining the emissions per visitor, it becomes evident that Finland, Sweden, and Norway exhibit the greatest levels of CO₂ emissions among nationalities. Regarding the weighted average fuel consumption per kilometre per passenger, Swedish visitors exhibit the highest fuel usage, followed by Spanish, Norwegian, and Finnish tourists. Despite the lowering weighted average fuel consumption per km of the aircraft over the investigated period, the number of tourist arrivals has increased, resulting in a rise in overall emissions.

We utilise various social carbon cost estimates from the literature to estimate our CO₂ emissions, which represent the monetary value of the harms caused by these emissions. This economic evaluation of emissions is contrasted with the tourism Gross Domestic Product (GDP) of the islands, revealing that the proportion of emission value (representing the detrimental effect of tourism) to tourism GDP (representing the economic activity provided by tourism) ranges from 0.08% to 3.11%, depending on the simulation.

In addition, by employing a tourism expenditure survey conducted by the Canary Islands Statistical Institute (ISTAC), we can accurately ascertain the magnitude by which the expense of the vacation package would rise in the event of the implementation of carbon taxes on airfare. We calculated the decrease in visitor arrivals by taking advantage of the increase in prices and the price sensitivity of tourist demand. A specific economic area's input-output model is developed using observable data. Using the 2015 regional Input-Output data from the European Commission project SOCLIMPACT, we use an Input-Output model to determine a decrease in the total regional value added. The decline ranges from 0.02% to 1.40%, depending on the particular simulation. When analysing the tourism industry, particularly the hotel sector, we expect a decrease in the sector's value added ranging from 1.61% to 8.40%.

Abstract 18

Perception of Airline Service Quality: Insights from User-Generated Content.

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KEYWORDS: Service quality, passenger satisfaction, airline attributes, service quality attributes.

ABSTRACT: Given the intense rivalry in the aviation sector, comprehending passengers is a significant aspect for airlines aiming to enhance service quality, customer satisfaction, and loyalty. As air travel continues its recovery from the COVID-19 pandemic and experiences growth compared to preceding years, the evaluation of service quality by passengers remains a major focus area for research in the aviation sector. This study aims to examine passenger perceptions among European airlines through an in-depth analysis of User-Generated Content (UGC). Additionally, the research investigates differentiation in perceptions across airline types, specifically between Low-Cost Carriers (LCCs) and Full-Service Carriers (FSCs). By analysing passenger experiences with leading European airlines, this research seeks to reveal the main themes and service quality attributes that contribute to passengers' overall satisfaction.

UGC has become a powerful tool for researchers, providing valuable insights into customer assessments. A systematic literature review has revealed that many scholars have previously employed surveys to evaluate service quality. Recently, researchers have acknowledged the advantages of UGC in conducting a comprehensive evaluation of passengers' flight experiences. The benefits of integrating UGC, particularly in the form of Online Customer Reviews (OCRs), include the incorporation of both textual reviews and associated numerical ratings, as well as access to large-scale datasets for in-depth analysis. Considering the significance of the aforementioned advantages, the study utilizes data retrieved from TripAdvisor, the world's largest travel guidance platform (TripAdvisor, 2023).

The primary objective of the research is to investigate passengers' perceptions of European airlines by utilizing genuine traveller-shared experiences. In addition, the research aims to identify differences and similarities in passengers' perceptions based on airline type, providing valuable insights into airline market segmentation.

The research is anticipated to make a substantial contribution to the knowledge base on European airline service quality, with practical implications for the industry. The distinction between Low-Cost Carriers and Full-Service Carriers enables a more comprehensive understanding of how diverse customer segments evaluate service quality attributes. This information can assist airlines in refining their services, adjusting to evolving passenger expectations, and customizing their offerings to specific customer groups.

Abstract 19

Overtourism: a Demand Analysis of Tourists' Perception.

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KEYWORDS: Overtourism, mass tourism, tourist destinations, tourism demand, sentiment analysis.

ABSTRACT: In recent decades, tourism has experienced an exponential worldwide growth. We have moved from 438 million travellers in the 1990s to 1461 million in 2019 (UNWTO, 2020). Tourism contributes to the economic development of regions. For instance, in the case of Spain and Italy, its contribution to GDP is larger than 10 per cent while in Croatia exceeds 20 per cent. Its continuous growth has led to the appearance of the phenomenon of overtourism in regions such as Japan, Barcelona, Amsterdam, Venice, and the Alps.

Overtourism can be defined as “the impact of tourism on a destination, or parts thereof, that excessively influences perceived quality of life of citizens and/or quality of visitors experiences in a negative way” or also as “destinations where hosts or guests, locals or visitors, feel that there are too many visitors and that the quality of life in the area or the quality of the experience has deteriorated unacceptably” (UNWTO, 2018). The excessive presence of tourists in a given place affects residents' daily lives generating congestion, noise and pollution, and also increasing the cost of living and housing prices. Besides these effects, overtourism is a phenomenon that also affects tourists. Travelling to a place on which you cannot visit the main tourist sites due to visitor caps or waiting in long queues just to see an emblematic building or take a photo makes vacations stressful and even an unpleasant process.

This paper provides a demand analysis in order to study tourists' perception of overtourism. The database is made up of reviews posted by tourists on Tripadvisor. These reviews correspond to the most visited tourist attractions in those cities and regions that are currently at risk of overtourism. These are Amsterdam, Barcelona, Croatia, Japan and Venice. The analysis is based on a sentiment analysis of reviews published in 2019 and 2023.

The main results of the analysis suggest that there is a high social awareness of overtourism among tourists. They manifest their willingness to collaborate in order to mitigate their effects. However, positive reviews of tourist attractions are in line with tourist attractions with no entrance fee. Thus, this analysis highlights the need to tackle overtourism, while highlighting the difficulty in implementing the right measure.

Abstract 20

Opaque Products: a Profitable Pricing Strategy for Airlines and a Popular Way of Travelling for Consumers.

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KEYWORDS: Pricing strategy, opaque products, blind tickets, tourism demand.

ABSTRACT: Tourism-related firms continuously deal with changing and uncertain demand. In the case of the air transport industry, airlines make use of different revenue management techniques in order to manage distressed inventory while maximizing revenues. Blind tickets are an ingenious pricing strategy which consists of selling surprise trips to customers who at the moment of purchase only know the set of possible destinations they may travel to. Once consumers pay, firms reveal all detailed information. In this paper, we develop a theoretical model in order to analyse to what extent this pricing strategy is profitable for airlines. Blind tickets may increase profits by up to 30 per cent.

However, our main theoretical contribution is to take into consideration consumers' risk aversion. Ignoring risk-aversion results in consumers without incentives to purchase these products and, therefore, losses for airlines up to 25 per cent. Regarding the demand side, this paper is the first one to test how customers perceive these products through sentiment analysis. Results show that more than 87% of the reviews posted by consumers are positive.

Additionally, individuals highlight that thanks to these innovative products, they end up travelling to initially undesired destinations, but end up delighted. Therefore, we show it is not only a profitable pricing strategy for airlines, but also for consumers and tourist destinations.

Abstract 21

Volcanic Eruptions and Tourism Prosocial Consumption.

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KEYWORDS: Volcanic eruptions, tourism expenditure, empathy mechanism.

ABSTRACT: This paper exploits a recent natural experiment to analyze the effect of volcanic eruptions on tourism expenditure. Using a Difference-in-Differences methodology, we find that volcanic eruptions have a positive impact on tourism expenditure, both aggregate expenditure and expenditure by category, and both during the eruption and the post-eruption period. We investigate the mechanisms behind the increase in expenditure. In particular, we investigate a price mechanism, a change in profile mechanism, a curiosity mechanism and an empathy mechanism.

For the price mechanism we could not use the CPI due to the lack of disaggregated data for the Canary Islands. Thus, we proxy the price level by using the diesel prices. Our analysis shows that the price level in La Palma did not increase higher than in the control islands. Moreover, previous literature shows that the demand diminished in the island indicating that both, general prices and tourist demand did not pressure a rise in prices. For the profile mechanism we compare the profiles before and after the volcano and did not obtain significant difference. Additionally, we tested the curiosity mechanism hypothesis by assuming that the tourist coming to the island to see the volcano could not book in advance given the nature of the phenomenon. Our results show that those who booked with less than 15 days or even a month spend less on the destination. This means that the rise in expenditure cannot be due to those tourists.

After discarding the previous mechanism, we tested the empathy mechanism with both, a theoretical and an empirical model. Our results show that the higher the bond that the tourist has with the local population, the higher the rise in expenditure on the destination. Thus, those tourists with friends or relatives or even a property in the island were those with higher rise in expenditure. Regarding the tourist without bonds with the islands, mainland Spain tourists rose their expenditure higher than foreigners. Moreover, we analyzed not only the active period but also three months after the last day of activity. Our results show that the rise in expenditure is not only sustained but even raised for the tourist with bonds with the islands while the foreigners reduce the expenditure.

To conclude, we obtained strong support for the empathy mechanism, prevailing over other mechanisms such as changes in prices, the profile of tourists, or simply curiosity. Our analysis suggests that tourist empathy with the affected community manifests through consumption, finding that prosocial consumption increases in the cultural identification of the tourist with the affected area.

Abstract 22

Satire and Social Critique in Tourism: Cartoons and Vignettes about Contemporary Tourism issues in Spanish Press.

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KEYWORDS: Comics - Cartoons - Caricatures, Satire, Social Critique, Tourism, Spain.

ABSTRACT: According to historical records there are precedents of cartoons in antique Egypt, Mesopotamia, antique Rome and Greece, and the pre-Columbian world. Reflecting through humour an argumentative and persuasive discourse, with reasons and emotions about the social representations that are analysed or questioned. Through an iconographic and semiotic analysis of the message, the text and the illustrations, the reader shares meanings by sublimating worries. From a universal language of interpretation of reality, the cartoon parodies through metaphor and irony, functioning as a catalyst in the formation of critical-reflexive thought. Beyond being humorous expressions, they have also evolved to become essential elements of political journalism and social critical analysis.

In relation to the topics of study, it is important to highlight that Spain is currently undergoing a complex and conflictive situation in some of its most iconic mature and consolidated tourist destinations. In which there is a phenomenon of overtourism, movements of protest and social discontent against touristification, as well as reactions of tourismphobia against the tourist sector and tourists. Comics and cartoons on tourism issues have been exponentially increasing their presence in the media, reflecting a current of public opinion that deals mainly with the most notorious negative impacts of tourism. These notably include rising rental prices for residential housing, environmental and noise pollution, rising costs of living and basic inputs, traffic jams, inequitable distribution of the benefits of tourist activity, displacement and exclusion of the resident population, and problems of coexistence between tourists and residents.

We present and analyse, from a novel perspective of the interpretative framework, comics and cartoons by recognised authors that we consider most and best represent the above mentioned social facts. Through interpreting text, narratives, as well as images, we examine the shared meanings and underlying social concerns. This approach helps us to understand how cartoons through satire, irony and exaggeration not only reflect aspects of social reality, but also the influence of media in the emerging and consolidating trends of opinions about tourism and its effects in society.

Abstract 23

Understanding Operational Models of Tourism Observatories.

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KEYWORDS: tourism observatories, decision-making, sustainable tourism.

ABSTRACT: The use of empirical data in tourism destinations has been recognized as key driver for more accurate decision-making (Font et al., 2023; Miller & Ward, 2005; Torres-Delgado et al., 2023). However, management research frequently diverges from practical management applications (Bansal et al., 2012). The “two-community” theory argues that this gap exists because of the differences between the research system and the policy making (Caplan, 1979). Bansal et al. (2012) highlight the need for boundary-spanning intermediary organizations for bridging the gap between management research and practice. In this context, tourism observatories act as such intermediaries aimed at transforming raw data into actionable knowledge for decision-makers in tourism destinations (Alvares & Perinotto, 2022).

However, little attention has been paid to tourism observatories in the scientific literature. Recent research on sustainable tourism measurement has primarily focused on developing indicators (Agyeiwaah et al., 2017; Baggio, 2019; Torres-Delgado & Saarinen, 2014), with less emphasis on governance issues (Moniche & Gallego, 2023; Rasoolimanesh et al., 2023). This research argues that effective monitoring of tourism destinations requires more than just a reliable indicator system. As knowledge creation in tourism is a multifaceted process (Crabolu et al., 2023), and destination stakeholders often lack knowledge and/or time for implementing evidence-based approaches (Torres-Delgado et al., 2023), there is a need for a responsible organization for developing indicators and/or knowledge within the destination. The UNWTO International Network of Sustainable Tourism Observatories (INSTO) provides practical evidence of the importance of tourism observatories. This network, comprised by 42 observatories as of December 2023, evidences the diverse focus and structures of tourism observatories depending on destinations needs (UNWTO, 2016).

The objective of this research is to explore different models of tourism observatories in destination specific contexts. For this, a multiple case study approach will be employed, analyzing 19 INSTO observatories from Argentina (1), Australia (1), Canada (2), Colombia (1), Greece (1), Guatemala (1), Ireland (1), Italy (1), Mexico (2), Philippines (1), Portugal (3) and Spain (4). The methodology combines semi-structured interviews and content analysis of relevant documents and reports. This approach allows for a better understanding of their tasks, stakeholder relationships and perceived usefulness for decision-makers. Inspired by the business model typology for Destination Management Organizations (DMOs) developed by Reinhold et al. (2019), tourism observatories will be classified upon two dimensions. On the one hand, the configurational complexity, which examines the engagement with singular or multiple stakeholder groups and whether the focus is on producing standardized knowledge or tailoring the knowledge to stakeholders. And on the other hand, perceived control, which examines the influence of the observatory over tourism policies and practices, and the type of relationships with destination stakeholders.

This research contributes to a deeper understanding of tourism observatories and their operational models. It also highlights the need for observatories to adapt their models to suit specific destination challenges. The main limitation of this research is the absence of the decision-makers perspective, which could be incorporated in further research. Additionally, outcomes from this study are expected to enhance the effectiveness of tourism observatories, in order to improve tourism management and sustainability practices in tourism destinations.

Abstract 24

Tourist Island Destinations Vulnerability in a Multi-Hazard and Multi-risk context.

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KEYWORDS: Island vulnerability, climate change, tourism dependence.

ABSTRACT: In the global context of tourism, islands represent unique and attractive tourist destinations that, despite their distinctiveness, face a series of substantial challenges related to their vulnerability to multi-hazard and multi-risk scenarios in the context of climate change. This study focuses on exploring and analyzing the vulnerability of island tourist destinations, with a special emphasis on the socio-economic ultraperipheral status within the European Union, as illustrated by the notable case of the Canary Islands. The geographical remoteness of these islands not only adds logistical complexity but also introduces unique challenges (Mycoo et al., 2022) that require attention and singular adaptive strategies.

Islands, due to their geographical nature, face natural hazards ranging from extreme climatic events to geological phenomena such as earthquakes and volcanic eruptions. Risks have been exacerbated in the contemporary era due to factors such as climate change (Arabadzhyan et al., 2021) and increasing exposure. The intersection of natural vulnerability with the economic dependence of these island regions on the tourism industry creates a complex and challenging dynamic. In particular, the Canary Islands, notorious for their natural beauty and tourist appeal, illustrate the tension between environmental fragility and the need for economic development.

Tourism, being a vital driving force for island economies, also contributes to their inherent vulnerability (Sharpley, 2001, Duro et al., 2021). The interconnection of the tourism sector with other economic areas generates a complex network of relationships, meaning that any disruption in tourism can have cascading effects across various sectors, and vice versa, from agriculture to all local services, commonly shared with residents. This phenomenon of impact chains amplifies the vulnerability of the islands to crises such as the COVID-19 pandemic, highlighting the fragility of economies dependent on tourism (Duro et al., 2021). The unique geographical situation of the islands poses additional challenges in terms of access to resources and emergency response capabilities. The distance from the mainland affects the speed at which resources and assistance can be mobilized in crisis situations. This logistical aspect adds an extra layer of complexity to risk management and emergency planning in island tourist destinations. Island regions are also characterized by complex governability, often adding government administrative layers, specific culture, rules and exemptions from the rules due to their lower economies of scale and limited resources. This can add complexity to the recovery from natural disasters. Indeed, lessons learned from past events underline the need for mitigation and adaptation strategies that address these specificities, particularly when the disaster risk management cycle is considered.

In summary, the vulnerability of island tourist destinations, especially those distant from the mainland like the Canary Islands (López-Díez, 2020), is a multidimensional phenomenon that combines natural risks, economic dependence, and complex sectoral interconnections. The effective management of this vulnerability requires holistic approaches that integrate emergency preparedness measures, economic diversification strategies, and sustainable environmental considerations. As tourism continues to be a crucial driving force, understanding and addressing these challenges become imperative to ensure the long-term resilience of island tourist destinations in a world characterized by uncertainty and global interconnection.

Abstract 25

Tourist Postcards of Gran Canaria: Origins and Social Representations.

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KEYWORDS: Gran Canaria, Projected image, Tourist postcards, Social representations.

ABSTRACT: Initially, access to the image was through photography and cinema, but postcards later projected the novelty of the image of the tourist destination and demonstrated the status of a privileged socio-economic class that could travel: the incipient urban bourgeoisie. This was the beginning of a "letter without an envelope", of the communication of the "public self": images that for the first time illustrated a personal or familiar trip.

We analyse old tourist postcards of Gran Canaria. The study was carried out through two exhibitions held in the city of Las Palmas de Gran Canaria (Institution "Gabinete Literario", postcards from the collection of Cayetano Sánchez and Gonzalo Hernández, and the Museum of the Cabildo de Gran Canaria "La Casa de Colón", with postcards from the collection of Vicente Rodríguez Suárez). Conceived as a representative compilation of the island's tourist postcards. We value the different discursive dimensions centred on the projection of elements of cultural identification of Gran Canaria, from the end of the 19th century, the first decade of the 20th century, to the 1980s, including the beginning of the tourism development in the 1960s. Providing an integral perspective of the beginning of the tourist offer, the material analysed reproduces clichés and stereotypes of the island based on the exotic, the remote or the adventure of an unknown destination. These varied iconographic images not only document the landscape and culture, but also represent a key element in the incipient formation of the island's tourist image through the projection of its supposed references of social identification. By analysing how certain cultural stereotypes of identity emerged and were perpetuated through postcards, we can obtain a more complete and nuanced view of the evolution of tourism in Gran Canaria.

The connotative focus on what should be observed is based on general cultural references about what is worth experiencing on a tourist trip. To do so, it alludes to iconic references that largely obviate the contextualising phenomena and processes that give them meaning as relevant elements in a spatio-temporal context. The selection of attributes considered worthy of becoming symbolic identifiers of the destination, which fit within these connotative strategies, ultimately encourage the creation and maintenance of cultural clichés appropriate to the objective of promoting an ideal of the destination in accordance with the dominant tourist imagery.

Abstract 26

Sustainable Tourism: Beyond Hospitality. A case study of EcoMarine Malta.

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KEYWORDS: sustainable tourism, community engagement, environmental conservation.

ABSTRACT: Sustainable tourism has evolved from a mere buzzword to a global imperative, emphasizing the need for responsible practices that extend beyond traditional hospitality frameworks. This abstract explores the belief that sustainable destinations cannot solely rely on eco-friendly accommodations but must integrate comprehensive sustainable experiences that engage local communities, respect cultural heritage, and prioritize environmental conservation. When executed thoughtfully, sustainable tourism becomes a potent tool for protecting the environment and fostering conservation efforts.

In this context, EcoMarine Malta emerges as a compelling case study, exemplifying how touristic activities can be harnessed to increase knowledge about the Mediterranean Sea while endorsing sustainable practices. The company's approach encompasses a holistic commitment to environmental stewardship, community engagement, and cultural preservation. EcoMarine Malta's initiatives are designed to provide tourists with memorable experiences and opportunities to actively contribute to preserving the delicate marine ecosystem. Through strategic partnerships and community involvement, the company has embedded sustainability into the fabric of its operations. The local communities are not mere spectators; they are active participants in crafting sustainable tourism experiences that showcase the richness of their cultural heritage.

One key facet of EcoMarine Malta's approach is the integration of educational elements into their touristic activities. The company goes beyond the conventional tourism model by providing guided tours incorporating scientific insights, transforming each excursion into an educational opportunity. Through these experiences, tourists gain a deeper understanding of the Mediterranean Sea's intricacies, learning about marine life, ecosystems, and their challenges.

The company's commitment to environmental conservation is evident in its research projects, with a particular focus on the Maltese dolphin population. By utilizing acoustic systems and collaborating with local authorities, EcoMarine Malta contributes valuable data to ongoing conservation efforts. This engagement not only enriches the scientific understanding of the marine environment but also underscores the company's dedication to being a responsible custodian of the seas.

Furthermore, EcoMarine Malta actively involves tourists in data collection, creating a symbiotic relationship where tourism becomes a means of supporting scientific research. Tourists, in turn, become ambassadors for marine conservation, carrying the knowledge gained during their experiences back to their communities.

EcoMarine Malta serves as a noteworthy case study, illustrating how sustainable tourism can and must offer experiences that respect the environment, resulting in powerful tools for conservation. By incorporating education, community engagement, and environmental conservation into its core principles, the company exemplifies a model for sustainable tourism that benefits not only tourists but also the local communities and the environment. Through such initiatives, sustainable experiential tourism emerges as a travel option and a transformative force for positive change, fostering a deep responsibility towards our planet, its diverse ecosystems and local communities and stakeholders.

By leveraging EcoMarine Malta as a case study, this research proposal seeks to provide insights that extend beyond its specific context, offering a replicable framework for other countries. The study aims to contribute to the broader discourse on sustainable tourism by demonstrating how the integration of sustainable experiences can serve as a powerful and adaptable tool for conservation worldwide.

Abstract 27

Addressing Coordination in Tourism-Led Economies: How coordination failures can arise even when economic agents know the path to Economic growth.

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KEYWORDS: General equilibrium theory, coordination failure, sustainable tourism growth, public good, efficiency.

ABSTRACT: Complex economic activities must be accomplished simultaneously by several economic agents with a certain degree of complementarity, to assure minimum quality levels requested by consumers. In this regard, we understand complementarity conditions as the action of an agent that affects and is affected by other agents' actions, requiring some level of coordination to achieve the desired goal. In total absence of coordination, the economy would move to an undesired equilibrium (bad equilibrium) that may arise even in perfect information conditions. I.e. agents know the good equilibrium, but they do not achieve it.

In the context of tourism, the need for coordination arises when understanding the complexity of the tourism product. Briefly, the latter can be defined as a composite good formed mainly by accommodation and catering services (private goods) and environmental attributes (public goods/ common pool resources) that enrich the tourism experience, shape the tourism image and, finally, foster the generation of value added at the destination. As a result of this complementarity, a proper provision of public goods is mandatory to attract high-quality tourists willing to pay more for these goods and to ensure long-lasting economic growth. This relationship is especially needed in mature destinations, which are currently facing increasing competition for cheaper ones.

To shed light on this issue, authors have developed a theoretical dynamic general equilibrium model. Briefly, It is a small-open economy, where capital and labour are perfect mobile and it is characterized by two types of sectors: the tourism sector and the rest of the economy. The former is disentangled into high-quality and low-quality tourism. High and low-quality tourists are defined similarly. Each one demands a complex good, including high/low quality tourist good (each one depending on its own type of tourist) and the public good; where each type of tourist pays a different price to enjoy it. More precisely, high-quality tourists are accommodated in dearer hotels and value more public goods (higher complementarity), but both, high-quality tourists and low-quality ones, share the environmental goods (environment, weather conditions, cultural heritage, etc). Given this difference in the willingness to pay for public goods, this can lead to an inefficient allocation of resources to maintain the quality/stock of the public good. In this case, as shown by the preliminary results, when the supply of the public good falls because of bad coordination, at stock or quality level, this impacts greater on high-quality tourists. As a result, the former are crowded out by low-quality tourists generating a lower economic growth (bad equilibrium).

The implications for mature destinations, well beyond the consolidation phase, are clear. A misallocation of resources due to the prevalence of coordination failures can make the difference between passing into decline as tourism destination or, in case of good coordination, entering in a rejuvenation phase. I.e. in order to reach the latter, improvements in tourism facilities should be made, vis-a-vis with proper management of public goods.

Abstract 28

Superyachts and Corporate Tourism: An integrated analysis.

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KEYWORDS: Superyachts, corporate entertainment, luxury tourism, 4Es framework.

ABSTRACT: The luxury tourism sector exceeds US\$ 17 billion in 2021, and it is anticipated to show a 15% rate of return from 2022 to 2030. Within this expansive market, a significant segment is constituted by the presence of superyachts. Superyachts are commonly defined as opulent, professionally crewed vessels, both motor and sailing propulsion, with lengths ranging from 24 meters to approximately 180 meters. These vessels may either be privately owned for personal use or owned and made available for chartering purposes.

For decades, superyachts have epitomized luxury and extravagance, catering to the discerning preferences of the ultra-wealthy. Renowned for their lavish amenities, stylish design, and culinary excellence, these vessels have long symbolized the pinnacle of opulent leisure. However, recently, there has been a significant change in the value proposition of superyachts, with an increasing emphasis on holistic wellness experiences. Today, boat owners and corporate tourists alike can access meticulously curated facilities, including cutting edge gyms, high-end spas, private cinema rooms, and luxurious salons. These amenities are designed to offer a comprehensive wellness encounter that addresses both the physical and psychological dimensions of wellbeing. As corporate tourism increasingly incorporates wellness travel, superyachts have become prime destinations for executives seeking relaxation, rejuvenation, and unparalleled luxury amidst breathtaking seascapes.

This study examines the growing connection between superyachts and the business corporate luxury tourism, and luxury charter markets. Given the increasing attention from corporations and interested stakeholders, this study seeks to clarify the complex aspects of luxury, including both physical and non-physical elements that together contribute to a subjective concept.

The main aim of this investigation lies on the acknowledgment of a significant change in the luxury industry, where the focus shifts from tangible belongings to intangible and experiential aspects. To analyse luxury experiences, the conceptual framework of Pine and Gilmore and the 4Es framework is used. Here, the study offers a self-reflective narrative that provides particular details on a superyacht charter experience, aiming to provide factual observations.

The results of this study highlight the changing nature of high-end corporate business entertainment and emphasise the significant influence that superyachts have in creating these experiences. Moreover, a qualitative analysis regarding the significance of collaborative creation in these high-end experiences and the essential role of genuineness is conducted. In conclusion, this study aims to deepen the understanding of the intricate interactions between superyachts and corporate entertaining within the luxury tourism sector.

Abstract 29

Blue Tourism: A Path Towards Sustainable Tourism Development in Blue Spaces.

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KEYWORDS: Blue tourism, sustainability, health and well-being.

ABSTRACT: Over time, there has been a standardizing trend in the analysis of territories that have similar natural characteristics, for example having a coastline, and consequently a generalization in the approach to the tourist offer in these territories. Currently, the competitiveness and sustainability of territories depends on a paradigm that is antagonistic to the one that for decades guided tourism planning and management, giving uniformity a place for differentiation and singularity. The landscape, aromas, flavours, sounds and textures associated with blue spaces constitute a symphony that simultaneously appeals to the different senses and that greatly contributes to the quality of visitors' experiences, but also to the quality of life of residents.

In this context, Blue Tourism emerges, which includes all tourist practices developed in aquatic environments, that is, which has as its main resource water in its multiple forms (seas, inland seas, rivers, reservoir lakes, streams, among others), and in the territories adjacent to it, have the concept of wellness intrinsic, that is, they contribute to health and well-being, and whose planning and development is based on a sustainability model (Brito & Silveira, 2023). It is a tourist product that, due to its characteristics, fits into the paradigm of Sustainable Tourism, and can contribute to the differentiation of Blue Spaces, promote employment and entrepreneurship, to attract investment, to mitigate seasonality, to complement other tourist offer, to identify and preserve material resources and intangible resources, in short to promote the sustainable development of territories.

Based on this theoretical framework, and the assumption that the relationship between human beings and water has a positive nature, which contributed to the residential and tourist attractiveness of Blue Spaces, we applied a questionnaire survey through the LimeSurvey platform to residents in Portuguese territory (born until 2008), with responses collected from 23 November 2022 to 26 April 2023 (five months), with 2930 valid responses obtained, with the aim of assessing the residential and tourist attractiveness of Blue Spaces, based in the relationship and impacts between proximity and contact with water (in the place of residence and/or in places of leisure and tourism) and people's health and well-being.

We aim to share the preliminary conclusions of this study which allow us to state that, for reasons of varying nature, for most people the presence of water in their territories is a determining factor when choosing holiday and/or visiting destinations; present their relationship with water and its impacts on their health and well-being, and the experiences related to water that they favor.

The conclusions drawn from this study allow Blue Spaces to guide their tourism planning and development strategy, to make their conventional and unconventional resources profitable for tourism, in a context in a context of sustainability.

Abstract 30

Dragon Fruit: Analysis of the potential development of Gastroturistic products through the use of neuromarketing techniques.

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KEYWORDS: Neuromarketing, consumer behavior, advertising strategies.

ABSTRACT: The pitaya, commonly referred to as the dragon fruit due to the peculiar shape of its protuberances, has experienced a significant increase in popularity internationally in recent years. This phenomenon is attributed to the outstanding physicochemical, nutritional, and organoleptic properties that distinguish it in the market. Although it is not a regular part of the daily diet, its unique visual appeal and nutritional profile have aroused interesting interest among consumers worldwide. However, given its unconventional position in the market, it is essential to explore the factors that impact the purchase and consumption of this exotic fruit.

To address this question, an experiment was conducted to analyze how the communication of health benefits and sector-supported promotion by professionals and industry references influences the decision to buy and consume dragon fruit. Furthermore, this study aimed to examine the emotional impact generated by these advertising strategies on consumers, as well as the fixation and directed attention towards the fruit during exposure to various content forms. Additionally, the possibility of these promotional actions having an effect on the willingness to pay for dragon fruit was also explored.

The methodology employed in this experiment integrated two techniques of neuromarketing: Eye Tracking and Face Coding. Eye Tracking was utilized to analyze the fixation and attention of consumers upon viewing images and videos of the dragon fruit in various states. This approach provided valuable information regarding which specific aspects captured the viewer's attention and how fixation was distributed during exposure to content related to the fruit.

On the other hand, Face Coding was implemented to evaluate the emotional response of consumers to various forms of content, including images, videos, and the consumption experience of the dragon fruit. This analysis allowed for the identification of emotions generated by the promotional strategies and determination of whether there were variations in the emotional response based on the approach used, as well as during the product tasting. The results of this study provide a detailed perspective on how specific advertising strategies impact the purchase and consumption of an unconventional fruit such as the dragon fruit. These findings not only could be useful for professionals in the sector, providing valuable insights for the formulation of more effective and consumer-centric campaigns, but they also suggest potential applications in the tourism sector. It is highlighted that the use of neuromarketing techniques does not replace, but complements, traditional techniques, generating information that would otherwise be inaccessible.

Abstract 31

Leveraging Neuromarketing and Neuroscientific approaches into persuasive Tourism Web Design and its usability: an exploration of tourists' cognitive experience enhancement.

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KEYWORDS: Neuromarketing, Cognitive engagement, Neuroscientific approach, Tourism websites, Neuro web design.

ABSTRACT: The primary goals of conventional tourist website design are visual appeal and data structure. Although aesthetics and practicality are critical, they fail to consider the more fundamental mental operations that impact vacation plans. A tourist's motivations stem from a web of feelings, recollections, and unspoken wants. Websites that are aesthetically beautiful but need to convert visitors into paying customers may result from traditional tactics that fail to tap into these motives adequately. Neuroimaging and psychological investigations offer insight into user attention, emotions, and decision-making processes, which is helpful for usability-related design improvements and might help develop persuasive design strategies. Websites aimed at attracting tourists have the potential to use dynamic features, engaging narratives, and striking imagery to evoke emotions in visitors. When used in the context of compelling design, narrative makes the brain feel something, which aids in recalling more than just taking in data.

This research uses neuroscientific methodologies to examine the compelling user experience design of tourist websites and see how basic principles of neuro-web design may make them more user-friendly, create a more enjoyable experience, and encourage more long-term engagement. This research indicates that destination marketers may benefit from incorporating digital interfaces with the complexities of the human brain to build sustainable tourism through websites that inform, evoke emotions in visitors, promote engagement, and affect decision-making.

Attracting people's minds and inspiring a desire to travel are vital to the tourist sector. Nevertheless, conventional site design must frequently captivate user intellect and impact travel choices. Businesses in the tourism industry might benefit from a more profound knowledge of their customers' mental and emotional processes when designing websites to provide more successful, engaging, and memorable online experiences. Additionally, optimizing website usability based on neuromarketing data and including components such as sensory signals, personalized content, and emotional drivers minimizes cognitive load, builds trust, and allows easy booking procedures. An all-encompassing strategy for tourist website design increases conversions and boosts company success by providing prospective visitors with a more convincing and user-friendly experience.

Developing informational, emotionally engaging websites that are easy to use may be achieved by delving into tourist cognition, resulting in a more favorable experience for users as they plan their trips. When making assumptions about user behavior, traditional web design frequently needs to catch up. By providing data-driven insights into how tourists think, neuromarketing allows designers to focus on visitors' attention, emotions, and decision-making processes while creating a website. Consequently, the design becomes more convincing and focused on the user's needs. Companies employing neuromarketing to their advantage in the tourism industry may stand out by providing customers with compelling and easy-to-use online experiences. In conclusion, the neuro web design is an intriguing new direction in optimizing online channels for sustainable tourism promotion. It offers unique chances to influence how tourists view and engage with destinations on the ever-changing internet. Websites that provide information, create emotional bonds with tourists, encourage interaction, and impact decision-making might help destination marketers develop sustainable tourism by integrating digital interfaces with the complexities of the human brain.

Abstract 32

Educational mismatch in the quality of employment in the European Tourism Sector. A Gender Perspective.

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KEYWORDS: Job quality, tourism sector, gender perspective.

ABSTRACT: The importance of job quality in the well-being of individuals is a matter of interest for developed countries, and is even included in the Sustainable Development Goals - Goal 8 on decent work - of the United Nations 2030 Agenda. International economic literature recognises the influence of quality employment on the well-being of individuals, as well as the existence of more unfavourable working conditions in sectors such as tourism and especially for vulnerable groups such as young people and women. However, these studies do not tend to adopt a sectoral perspective and are usually carried out at the country level, leaving aside the presence of institutional factors that could arise when making an international comparison. On the other hand, there is a dearth of work that includes educational mismatch in the definition of quality employment, despite the effects that this misallocation of resources has on individuals and society. Thus, this paper analyses the determinant factors of obtaining a quality job in the tourism sector at the European level, taking into account individual and contextual factors in each country that allow us to study what part of the heterogeneity observed is explained by the heterogeneity between countries and what part is explained by the differences between individuals in each country. In addition, and given the importance of the employment situation of women in the hospitality industry, we consider analysing this issue from a gender perspective. To do so, we employ a random-constant multilevel logit model using supranational data from the 2018 European Wage Structure Survey (EES-18) and other European statistical sources.

The originality of this work lies in four sections: The sectoral perspective, by carrying out the analysis in the tourism sector given its specific characteristics and its importance in Europe. The international comparison, which allows us to capture the extent to which the institutional heterogeneity between these countries affects working conditions and the precariousness of employment. The gender perspective, which allows us to compare the situation of women and men in Europe when it comes to finding quality employment in this sector. And the incorporation of educational mismatch in the definition of quality employment, not only because of its importance and impact on European economies but also because it is influenced by institutional factors such as the labour structure of each country or educational policies.

Abstract 33

Social Media and Influencer Marketing in Luxury Tourism: Their Role on the Customer's Decision-Making Process.

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KEYWORDS: Luxury hospitality, travel influencers, social media.

ABSTRACT: The advent of social media in the early 2000s brought about a significant paradigm shift in how individuals interact with each other in the online and digital world. Initially, social networks served as a tool for introducing new modes of communication, but over time, they have evolved into platforms that occupy a significant portion of our daily lives. In addition to messaging, social media now enables us to share content, make calls video calls, engage in e-commerce, comment, and stay informed. As a result, they have become an integral part of our daily routine, with users navigating them organically and seamlessly. Consequently, companies have recognized the strategic value of social media in promoting their brands and products while establishing more sustainable relationships with users in a non-intrusive manner (Feng et al., 2021). Social media marketing refers to the actions taken on one or more social media platforms to promote, inform, or communicate a brand's story and products or services (Aydin, 2020). Social networks offer businesses an enormous potential to connect with their customers more deeply, emotionally, and less intrusively. Influencer collaboration is one of the several actions that can be taken as part of a social media marketing campaign. According to Lou and Yuan (2019), a social media influencer is a content creator who has attained expertise in a specific area and has cultivated a substantial following by providing valuable content on social media. From this perspective, travel influencers specialize in creating travel-related content on social media, which can influence their communities' decision-making processes (Jang et al., 2021).

Luxury travel brands differ in communication and behaviour on social media compared to non-luxury brands. As marketing specialists manage social media accounts to influence customer decision-making, non-luxury brand communication primarily focuses on sales promotion and positioning. In contrast, luxury brands communicate to create dreams and reinforce their brand philosophy (Xie & Lou, 2020). This paper explores the impact of social media marketing, specifically luxury travel influencer marketing, on the decision-making process of luxury travellers. The paper aims to identify the characteristics of luxury travel companies' social media marketing behaviour, understand how luxury travellers utilize social media influencers during their decision-making process, and evaluate the value of travel influencers for luxury travel companies. The methodology involved reviewing tourism journals published in the last 15 years focused on social media marketing in luxury tourism. The review underscores the importance of social media marketing in luxury tourism, highlighting the role of influencers in creating a brand image, generating consumer aspirations, and influencing purchase decisions. Travel influencers are recognized as valuable tools in inspiring and informing travellers, particularly during the initial stages of the customer journey. However, the literature review also underscores a research gap regarding travel influencer marketing in luxury tourism, emphasizing the need for further scholarly inquiry and empirical studies.

Abstract 34

Intellectual and Emotional Responses: Neuromarketing in Botanical Gardens.

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KEYWORDS: Botanical garden, visitor experience, emotional marketing, destination loyalty, visitor research, travel behaviour ecotourism, neuromarketing.

ABSTRACT: This article explores the dual experience in botanic gardens, studying the interaction between visitors' intellectual and emotional responses. It aims to shed light on the intricate connections between visitors' satisfaction, loyalty and sensory engagement. Thus, intellectual stimuli, such as educational exhibits and emotional stimuli, such as aesthetically pleasing scenery or scent, can collectively contribute to overall visitor satisfaction (Moser, 2023). Previously, some authors have studied how intellectual and emotional constructs may determine satisfaction and loyalty, but not in botanical garden settings (Yeh et al., 2020; Ghorbanzadeh, 2021; Elbaz et al., 2023). On the other hand, the integration of disruptive technologies such as augmented reality (AR) and virtual reality (VR) can enhance visitors' experience (Giraldi et al., 2022; Halkiopoulos et al., 2022; Garzón-Paredes & Royo-Vela, 2023).

Innovatively, our study in botanical garden literature will incorporate advanced technologies, such as Virtual Reality (VR) and Augmented Reality (AR), to obtain information on visitors' intellectual responses at the botanical garden. We shall integrate these technologies with a web survey to capture visitors' intellectual dimensions. The fieldwork will occur in the Botanical Garden "Viera y Clavijo". Additionally, we will focus on visitors' emotional dimensions, utilising neuromarketing techniques, such as eye-tracking in the Botanical Garden "Viera y Clavijo". Both data will be collected in March 2025. Furthermore, we will use monitoring software to analyse the emotions expressed on social media about the Botanical Garden "Viera y Clavijo".

This research's expected results enhance the promotion of botanical gardens and deepen our understanding of visitors' cognitive and emotional interactions with nature. The transformative potential of technology in fostering more engaging and meaningful connections between visitors and the natural environment will be elucidated. Integrating digitalisation and technology is expected to yield substantial improvements in visitor experiences, particularly in their intellectual and emotional responses. Moreover, its practical implications may assist garden managers and tourism experts in botanic gardens in improving management strategies through emotional interventions rather than cognitive ones in botanic gardens. Despite the acknowledged limitations, this study contributes to enriching the discourse on the visitor experience.

Abstract 35

From White Star's to White Elephants: Belfast's regeneration and rehabilitation through the Titanic.

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KEYWORDS: Maritime heritage, tourism regeneration, sectarian tensions.

ABSTRACT: This paper is an examination of Belfast's tourism-orientated regeneration and rehabilitation through its maritime heritage, history of shipbuilding, and birthplace of the ill-fated Titanic. At its Victorian heights the Belfast shipyard in Northern Ireland, with its trident shaped prongs across the Lagan, employed some 35,000 shipyard workers - a predominantly "closed-shop" Protestant workforce. This is where the gigantic Olympic class White Star steamships were designed and built, fitted out for transatlantic voyages. The Titanic was built on Queen's island over a period of two years, and taxi drivers will tell tourists "It was alright when it left here!" 46,000 tons in weight; carrying 2,435 passengers but with only twenty lifeboats for 1,178 people: the Titanic sank on 15 April 1912 with the tragic loss of approximately 1,600 lives. Their names are engraved on a memorial on the slipways behind Belfast's new Titanic Experience - a shimmering new multi-million pound tourist attraction of high-tech projections, holograms and amusement park style ride through the construction of the fated ship. It was opened in 2012, an hundred years later, as one of Northern Ireland's five signature attraction points developed for 'international standout' recognition (NIAO 2011: 2). It consolidates the soubriquet for Belfast as 'Titanic Town' (Bryan 2012) after Roger Michell's 1998 'Troubles'-related comedy Titanic Town as opposed to James Cameron's romantic tragedy Titanic [1997]).

Indestructible but culpable, the Titanic exhibition space is a metonym for the people of Belfast. It is promoted as a post-conflict peace dividend bringing international tourists to Northern Ireland (cf. Smith 2006) but is also critiqued as a new commercial memoryscape - with hulking 'credibility armour' (Grek-Martin 2023) - devoid of the tensions of the Troubles; a bland new history that avoids the Unionism of the workplace and brutal expulsion of Catholics to the clang of 'Queen's island confetti' (Royle 2011: 57) stolen rivets used in riots. Here the NI Tourist Board are drawing attention away from the polarised city with its centuries old history of protest and riot, and the terrorism and armed conflict through the 1970s and 1980s. For tourism scholars Causevic and Lynch (2011) the peace dividend gives rise to a Phoenix tourism. For Marxist literary critic George Legg (2018: 185), the result is a 'fakeland' as the capitalist spectacle disseminates sedation over sectarianism. It is a monoculture of bourgeois accumulation that excludes working class protagonists of any community. Boredom and apathy are the new repressive order for twenty-first century Belfast's public for Legg. They are subdued by the monotony of capital and mortgage aspirations to live at a remove from the confines of the conflict. The corporate multiculturalism that is being promoted in its place is empty of semiotic meaning - with CS Lewis Narnia murals painted over Loyalist inscriptions; a ban on any flags in the Titanic Quarter apartments, effectively neutralizing the gains from overturning the Flags and Emblems (Display) Act of 1954 that had de facto deemed the Irish flag a 'provocative emblem' (CAIN 2021); and a disposition of disdain for those caught up in the cross-community animosity. The suggestion in this writing is that a bomb-ravaged landscape is better than bland landscape (cf. McCrone) in this deindustrialized tourist destination and yet testimony from visitors to the Titanic Experience suggests otherwise: that the new Titanic Quarter is an example of tourism lite; good interactive stuff; a poignant love story for viewing next to the largest film set in the world. This paper uses long-term engagement with the site, with contemporary interviews and historical records to show the complexities and tensions in regenerating and rehabilitating the largest waterfront area in Europe. The conclusion is that local participation has not entirely quenched the sectarian flames as post-conflict scholars suggest (cf. Lagarense and Walansendow 2015).

Abstract 36

Technology Usage in Visitor Attractions: Leveraging Big Data from the Wi-Fi network.

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KEYWORDS: Visitor behavior, big data, tourism management.

ABSTRACT: Prior to the onset of the Covid Pandemic in 2020, it was already clear that certain forces were at work that signified the tourism sector (like many other sectors of the economy) had already entered the start of a “new paradigm”. The forces of technological disruption through digitisation and robotics were already in evidence in certain sub-sectors of the tourism sector as was an advancing recognition that “Climate Change” and its implication(s) would soon require more immediate attention. Finally, the movement to the Experience Economy has become manifest. This paper focuses in one of the pillars of the new paradigm in the tourism marketplace.

The research seeks to enhance an understanding of visitor behaviour at the Cliffs of Moher, Irelands most visited natural attraction through the use of big data from the Wi-Fi network. The researchers’ gained access to “anonymised data” with 4.7 million observations related to the movements of visitors at the site and this data was supplemented by weather data during the relevant periods. The data available on the profile of visitors was constrained by the screening questions that visitors completed to gain access to the Wi-Fi so the study and importantly the number of questions was limited. Resultantly, the study is very much exploratory in nature yet nonetheless the large volume of data does provide some very interesting findings. The study provides data on the nationalities of visitors to the site that corroborates previous data sampling of visitors by the authors. Moreover, that data provides excellent insights on visitor movement throughout the site and could provide the foundation for visitor management at the site during peak periods. The analysis of the data also reveals insights on the length of time visitors engage with Wi-Fi at the site and also gives insights on the breakdown of Wi-Fi usage as the tourist moves through the outdoor and indoor focal points at the site. The data also provided insights on how the weather impacts on the length of time visitors spend at the site.

The results based on the initial trawl of the very large volume of data provides some very encouraging insights which could be significantly enhanced if more discrete data was available from such large volumes of data. To that end the authors have got agreement from the management of the site to change the screening question to gain access to the Wi-Fi. The new screening questions will allow us to gain much greater granular data that could significantly enhance our understanding of visitor behaviour at the site. It is our expectation that some of this preliminary data will become available in the Spring of 2024, and we hope to present these additional findings, if available in Gran Canaria in June.

Abstract 37

Analysis of Interdependencies in tourism: The case of Canary Island.

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KEYWORDS: Machine learning; Tourism; hierarchical patterns; interdependencies.

ABSTRACT: The interest in studying tourist profiles is indeed increasing, as evidenced by various research papers (Ferreira and Perks, 2022; Alhothali et al., 2022; Akgün et al., 2021; Domènech et al., 2023 and Ardelean and Badulescu, 2022) where the importance of understanding tourists' characteristics, preferences, and behaviors has been highlighted. However, the different tourism activities that can be carried out in a destination are interconnected, not only due to the characteristics of the tourism offer, but also the tourists' profile. The application of a connectivity analysis serves to not only recognize the connections among different tourist activities, gender preferences, and seasonal variations, but also unveils the hierarchical framework inherent in these components.

The fundamental concept underlying this approach is to emphasize that not all patterns hold equal significance in constructing a tourist profile. Understanding the hierarchical arrangement – certain activities acting as primary attractions while others function as complementary offerings to enrich the overall experience – offers valuable insights for destination managers in efficiently allocating resources and enhancing the visitors' overall experience. The utilization of Association rules (Agrawal et al., 1993) in this research emphasizes the most crucial patterns at each hierarchical level. This innovative methodology employs data analytics, network theory, and statistical techniques to unveil the intricate network of connections among various tourist activities. In this sense, we use a large public database from the Canary Islands (almost 165.000 tourists observed from 2018 to 2022) including attractions visited, services consumed, socioeconomic and demographic characteristics, as well as the seasonal fluctuations in tourist numbers, to discern not only the activities that are most favoured by visitors, but also the hierarchical connections that exist among them.

Results shows different profiles acquired for individuals who are both willing to offer compensation and those who are not willing. Similarly, these results could be used to implement some policy recommendations to maximize the resource allocation and tourist satisfaction.

Abstract 38

The Role of Water Tariffs in Water use in the hospitality industry.

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KEYWORDS: Water management, price elasticity, tourism industry.

ABSTRACT: Despite low water consumption in tourist activities, in dry regions with high water stress, pressure on local water resources increases. This pressure intensifies when comparing direct water consumption by tourists and residents, and becomes more relevant when considering the environmental impact of wastewater generated by the tourism industry in sensitive local ecosystems. This situation highlights the urgent need to improve water management in the tourism industry to adapt to climate change and implement practices and policies that promote water efficiency, conservation, and comprehensively address water cycle management.

Accommodation establishments have access to information, technologies, and practices that could result in water savings, reduced operating and infrastructure maintenance costs, and an improvement in their reputation in terms of sustainability and CSR. However, as they share infrastructure and networks with residential consumers at the local level, they are affected by similar tariff structures and standards without solid financial incentives. Indeed, promoting tourism activities by reducing the cost of water is consistent with public policies at the local level that encourage tourism growth. Previous studies have shown the low importance of water bills in tourist businesses, despite the economic value that the resource brings. However, the lack of detailed information and the stability of water prices have resulted in few studies addressing price elasticity estimation and its application in the design of efficient tariffs. This research contributes to this literature in five specific areas: a) we estimate the price elasticity of water demand in tourist accommodations in three municipalities with different tariff structures; b) using data that includes the characteristics of each establishment, we estimate demand elasticity for different categories, isolating the heterogeneity of establishments and tourist destinations; c) we explore the impact of the tariff structure by analyzing the sensitivity of establishments to marginal and average water prices; d) we estimate the long-term sensitivity of water demand; e) we evaluate how the profitability of water consumption in relation to income can influence consumption decisions.

Using a comprehensive database containing water consumption data from 306 observed large water users' tourist establishments over 48 periods from 3 tourism intensive municipalities from the Canary Islands, the results show that water demands are inelastic and negative in all three municipalities, although they exhibit different magnitudes. In all three cases, water demands respond to the average service price. The price elasticity of water in the municipality of Pájara is equal to -0.92, while in San Bartolomé de Tirajana and Arona, it reaches -0.37 and -0.56, respectively. The low levels of water prices, which explain the reduced weight of water expenditure on total establishment expenditure, justify the low sensitivity of demand to prices. However, in the municipality where prices are substantially higher (Pájara), price sensitivity has been detected. In fact, these establishments have on average a 25.5% lower water consumption per overnight stay compared to establishments in other municipalities.

Therefore, the results indicate that it is possible to encourage more efficient water use in tourist establishments through differentiated tariffs based on the size of user categories. This practice would also improve distributive effects and equity of water prices in tourist destinations.

Abstract 39

Analysing Evolving Perceptions of Customer Satisfaction in luxury hotels.

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KEYWORDS: Sentiment analysis, post-pandemic perceptions, destination recovery.

ABSTRACT: As the global tourism landscape deals with the consequences of the COVID-19 pandemic, understanding tourist sentiments is crucial for destination recovery. This study investigates tourists' post-pandemic perceptions in the Canary Islands, drawing on insights from online hotel reviews. The study addresses an important gap in the literature by examining the complex relationship between traveller sentiments, destination preferences, and the unique challenges posed by the pandemic.

To capture the complexity of tourists' sentiments, this study employs sentiment analysis and topic modelling techniques on a comprehensive dataset of online hotel reviews. Leveraging Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA) and VADER sentiment analysis tool, the study extracts patterns, reveals underlying preferences and dissects satisfaction factors from the rich textual data

The findings reveal multifaceted patterns in tourist sentiment, highlighting critical factors such as service quality, amenities, and the profound impact of the pandemic on travel experiences. Through the clever use of topic modelling and sentiment analysis, the research provides a nuanced understanding of the emotional tones embedded in the reviews, presenting a comprehensive interpretation of tourists' evolving perceptions and expectations.

This research represents a significant step forward in understanding the dynamics of tourist sentiment in the post-COVID-19 era, particularly in the context of the Canary Islands. The integration of sentiment analysis and topic modelling not only contributes valuable insights to the academic discourse, but also has practical implications for the tourism industry. By acknowledging the evolving landscape of traveller expectations, destination management authorities can tailor strategies to ensure a resilient and satisfying tourism experience in the Canary Islands, facilitating an effective recovery of the global tourism sector. This study encourages further exploration of the dynamics of tourist sentiment following a pandemic, and provides a foundational framework for future research in destination recovery and management

Abstract 40

Procedures for Classifying Alternatives: An application in the tourism field.

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KEYWORDS: Multicriteria decision, Ranking, Borda-Condorcet rule.

ABSTRACT: In this work, the problem of selecting or ordering alternatives based on the values of certain attributes evaluated for each of them is considered. This is equivalent to establishing a ranking based on the scores given by several individuals to the different alternatives. To build a ranking, indices are defined that assign a value to each of the alternatives. One way to define an index consists in calculating the weighted sum of the attribute values. There are several procedures for choosing weights (normalization, hierarchical analytical process, weights based on entropy measurements, the best-worst method, principal component analysis, etc). Once the weights assigned to each attribute have been selected, the index value is calculated for each alternative, and the alternatives are ordered according to the values obtained. The values of the weights chosen can influence the resulting ranking. Only when it happens that for any pair of alternatives one of them dominates or is equivalent to the other, does a single ranking result, except for changes in the positions for equivalent alternatives. However, taking into account the dominance relationship, information can be obtained about the possible positions of the alternatives analyzed for any ranking obtained by the weighting method. In fact, it occurs for any method that respects the dominance relation.

A different method to construct a ranking is based on the Borda-Condorcet rule. This method is based on the pairwise comparison of alternatives. In this case, the ordering of the alternatives is determined by the eigenvector of the Borda-Condorcet matrix corresponding to the eigenvalue with the maximum absolute value (spectral radius). That is, the index that provides the ranking is this eigenvector, for which all components are positive (Perron-Frobenius theorem). The first step in obtaining the ranking consists in determining a partition of the set of alternatives, between whose elements there is a dominance relationship, and subsequently, the Borda-Condorcet index is calculated for each member of the partition.

Using notions from multi-criteria decision theory, such as the dominance relation, the weighting method, and the Borda-Condorcet criterion, an analysis is carried out of the set of Spanish cities included in the URBANTUR 2022 report ("Tourism Competitiveness Monitor of Spanish urban destinations", published by Exceltur). In this report, dedicated to urban tourism, a set of attributes grouped into six pillars is considered, and the value of the index for each pillar is calculated, and also the value of a global index, for the 22 Spanish cities of greatest tourist relevance, giving rise to a global ranking and also by pillars of these cities. The 22 cities analyzed represent 87.2% of urban tourism and 23% of Spanish tourism. The objective of this work is to expand the analysis carried out in URBANTUR considering the same attributes used in this report. The index used is analyzed and a Borda-Condorcet index is calculated for the cities considered.

Abstract 41

UNESCO Creative Cities in the Inland-Centre of Portugal.

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KEYWORDS: UNESCO creative cities network; creative cities in the inland-centre of Portugal; tourism and creative cities; swot analysis of creative cities.

ABSTRACT: The UNESCO Creative Cities Network was created in 2004 to promote cooperation with and among cities that have identified creativity as a strategic factor for sustainable urban development. The Network now counts 350 cities in more than one hundred countries which currently make up this network work together towards a common objective: placing creativity and cultural industries at the heart of their development plans at the local level and cooperating actively at the international level.

In the Centre of Portugal, there are six UNESCO Creative Cities, three of which are located inland. Due to their location, these cities have specific characteristics and have become areas which, over the last few years, have seen a systematic decrease in population, with progressive ageing and, at the same time, increased difficulty in keeping and retaining younger people. Tourism has been one of the activities that, in all these cities and in a joint action between the public, private and social sectors, has contributed most to economic dynamism, combined with creativity and innovation.

We propose a comprehensive approach, drawing up a SWOT analysis for each case, a summary of the most relevant economic activity, how they have incorporated the status of Creative Cities into everyday life and cultural programming.

We will also highlight the most important aspects related to communication strategies, particularly on digital channels, and assess their reputations as tourist destinations.

Finally, suggestions for development and/or improvement will be made, bearing in mind the objectives inherent in the UNESCO Creative Cities Network and how the specificities of each of the cities can achieve competitive and sustainable advantages in and through it.

We aim to contribute to a more detailed knowledge of the reality associated with Creative Cities, particularly those located inland, which are therefore faced with challenges and limitations that they want to face and overcome.

Contributions to science, management, and operators, public and private, are envisaged.

For science, as we do not know of any identical study, to date, which allows a comparative analysis. In addition, the growth and development of territories through distinctive factors associated with their tangible and intangible Heritage, being strategically important, needs more contributions from the literature. For the management of the UNESCO Creative Cities Network itself, which will have access to new data on the current reality and future perspectives, as well as the Creative City team on site. For operators, touristic and others, due to the observation of a reality that, susceptible to evolution, implies assertive actions, generating products and services with greater added value, designed through more detailed knowledge of market realities, more identified with consumers' needs and expectations.

Abstract 42

Outbound Tourism and Economic and Social Risks: Between the Pandemic and Regional Conflicts.

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KEYWORDS: Tourism and risk; economic, and social risks; pandemic and regional conflicts; outbound tourism markets.

ABSTRACT: Between December 2019 and October 2023, three events of exceptional impact and scope occurred sequentially: the COVID-19 pandemic, the invasion of Ukraine by Russia, and the war between Israel and Hamas. While at first, they were all confined to certain regions, their direct and/or indirect effects quickly became global.

Few times have such damaging circumstances almost simultaneously hit the world, so intensely and with such incisive effects, particularly in the economic, and social dimensions.

Tourist activity is also highly exposed and sensitive to events of this nature because it includes the perception of risk, which has a considerable influence on tourists' behavioural variables.

We propose a study that combines the effects on seven of the main outbound tourism markets - China, the United States, Germany, the United Kingdom, France, Italy, and Spain - and that, in these countries, surveys and analyses for some of the main socio-economic indicators: population, GDP per capita, inflation rate, unemployment rate, savings rate, outbound flows, and outbound tourism expenditure.

The evaluation of the indicators mentioned above and over the years in question will allow us to establish, using panel data and time series, because they originate from different realities, recommending double readings, common and specific.

We aim to analyse the movements recorded, which, whether stable, positive, or negative, allow us to conclude on the similarities and differences between the countries; the space of each one as an outbound tourism country; and the reading of their populations in the face of atypical years.

Evaluating the above-mentioned indicators over the years in question will make it possible to establish a dynamic analysis using descriptive statistics, because they originate from different realities, advocating dual readings, both common and specific.

Given the wide-ranging scope of the analysis, contributions are expected for science, management and public decision-makers, considering (i) the lack of studies with a methodology that uses such a complementary and recent series of indicators; (ii) the reading of a comparative analysis of the results, demonstrating realities with common and distinctive features; (iii) the support that central, regional and local authorities can provide in the face of these facts and circumstances.

This work is an integral part of a set of three ongoing papers by the same authors and with an identical approach methodology: this one, which covers the main outbound tourism markets; another, which focuses on the main inbound tourism markets; and, finally, a third, where a comparative analysis of the results obtained is carried out. This is, therefore, a partial approach to a topic that will gain consistency when seen from a global perspective, that is, with the conclusion of the three ongoing works. On the other hand, there are other factors, apart from the consequences of the pandemic and the conflicts in question, which can influence the economic and social indicators of countries and their populations. In addition, outbound tourism can be influenced by factors other than those mentioned. Therefore, this is an approach that adapts to the time and circumstances but does not exhaust the alternative scenarios.

Abstract 43

Crime Perceptions and Urban Tourism: A Systematic Literature Review.

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KEYWORDS: Crime, Risk Perceptions, Perceive Risks, Urban Tourism, Cities.

ABSTRACT: When tourists travel from their place of residence to a tourist destination, perceptions of risk are often present since tourists are outside their “comfort zone.” Many concerns among tourists are linked to criminal activities. Crime has long been studied in the fields of social sciences and tourism, since it is a common occurrence and can affect tourist destinations. Risks of this nature, particularly petty crime, tend to be prevalent in urban destinations.

As a result, the most touristy areas of cities often become crime hotspots, which may eventually influence tourists’ behaviors and consumption patterns. Simultaneously, the increase in tourism can exacerbate criminal activity, affecting not only tourists but also tourism-related businesses. On the other side of the spectrum, places with a history of crime can become a tourist attraction; however, for the average tourist, safety remains one of the most crucial attributes that destinations can offer (Seabra et al., 2020).

Given the comprehensive nature of this topic, the present work provides a systematic literature review, utilizing the SCOPUS and WoS databases to obtain a more detailed analysis of these concepts, organized into four categories: Cities and Crime; Tourists and Crime; Urban Residents and Crime; Crime as a Tourist Attraction.

Abstract 44

The Uneven way to renewables deployment: Specificities of island destinations.

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KEYWORDS: Tourism destination, renewables deployment, social acceptance, NIMBY syndrome, Q-Method.

ABSTRACT: Tourism destinations must transition to renewable energy to meet global decarbonization commitments and align with tourists' climate action preferences. Among the potential actions, deploying renewable energy stands out, alongside energy saving and efficiency measures. However, in recent years, residents in many regions have opposed renewable energy projects, driven by various motivations. The NIMBY (Not In My Backyard) syndrome has often explained this resistance. Since the late 1970s, NIMBY has been used to analyze public opposition to facilities perceived as health risks (e.g., landfills, nuclear waste sites) or undesirable (e.g., prisons). However, many authors argue that this approach is too simplistic and propose multidimensional frameworks to explain social perceptions and behaviors. Environmental, landscape-based, distributive, and participative arguments are also considered potential drivers of resistance to local interventions.

This paper aims to contribute to the literature by exploring why people reject necessary infrastructure in their surroundings, using Lanzarote in the Canary Islands as a case study. This 800 km², densely populated island is a hotspot for both tourism and biodiversity, attracting nearly 3 million tourists annually, with around 40% of its territory under protection. The island's volcanic and sandy landscapes are not only valuable tourist assets but also integral to its cultural identity. The regional government is implementing a renewable energy plan primarily based on energy productivity criteria, often overlooking environmental and landscape impacts. By labeling wind energy projects as urgent, they may bypass some environmental and land planning regulations. Many residents fear that external companies will control the energy sector and reap the benefits, while locals bear the negative impacts.

A Q-method-based study is being conducted to identify the diverse motivations behind the resistance to wind energy deployment on the island. Participants are asked to express their opinions on a set of statements representing different viewpoints and aspects of the issue. These opinions are organized in a Q-sort grid, where participants rank the statements based on their agreement or disagreement. Through inverted factor analysis techniques, patterns or factors are identified based on the correlations between participants' responses, clustering them into groups. The goal is to uncover commonalities and discrepancies to support decision-making processes that build consensus around energy transition.

Twenty-three representatives from various social groups, including entrepreneurs, large and small firms, environmentalists, the energy sector, agriculture and water sectors, and cultural associations, were selected to complete the Q-sort questionnaire. Preliminary results indicate that the NIMBY syndrome alone cannot explain the complexity of social motivations behind the rejection of renewable energy projects. Cluster analysis reveals that the majority support an energy transition guided by environmentally protective, landscape-respectful, distributive, and participative principles. Only a few participants reject renewables outright. The study identifies pathways for consensus-building, highlighting participation and equity as the most significant drivers. The unique characteristics of islands with significant tourist relevance are also emphasized. Residents' perceptions include concerns about tourists' reactions to significant landscape changes due to renewables deployment, which they believe might outweigh any disaffection towards the island's non-alignment with global climate action.

Abstract 45

Critical Success Factors of Wine Tourism Regions.

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KEYWORDS: Wine tourism, Critical factors, Motivation, Barriers, Satisfaction.

ABSTRACT: Wine tourism is a form of alternative tourism that has attracted much attention in recent years. Nowadays, wine tourism is one of the most important and most promising types of tourism, given that it is linked to the new consumption patterns of tourists, based on the importance of the experience, as well as on a shorter duration and greater frequency in the number of visits. Moreover, it can be considered as a strategic element in the wine-producing countries. So, the development of a wine Tourism Destination policy and positioning based on tourist's experiences, is crucial for tourism destination success. The appeal of wine regions can be based on "difference of place". Also, the term "touristic terroir" is used in order to describe the combination of physical, cultural and natural environments that give each region its distinctive appeal as a destination for wine tourists.

The aim of this research paper is to examine critical factors, which contribute to the success of the development of wine tourism destinations. Moreover, research; try out to identify the profile of tourists who are interested in wine tourism, as well as to investigate motivation factors for visiting a wine tourism destination and wineries.

An exploratory research was undertaken in order to gain a better understanding. A qualitative research was undertaken in order to gain a better understanding of "wine Destination success factors" the motives and barriers of wine Tourists. Then a quantitative research, was carried out by the means of questionnaire. 266 usable questionnaires were collected using a convenient sampling method. The data analysis showed that the target audience of wine tourism comprised of middle-aged or older individuals, having a high annual income, and rather high educational level. Results indicate that the products and services offered by wineries and the appeal of the destination are the key incentives. So, Results reveal that the critical factors that determine a destination success in developing wine Tourism are " PGI/PDO quality certifications", "Local Wine Sales", "Availability of Wineries to offer Wine Tours", "Staff knowledge" "Staff kindness", "Wine Tasting Events", "Infrastructure of the place", "Accommodation Facilities".

The most important motivation factor in order to visit a wine destination according to the respondents was "to taste local wines and cuisine". Other motivation factors were "gain experience", "increase knowledge about wine", "increase ability to recognize and purchase quality wine", "meet wine experts", "having fun", "relaxation", and finally "learn about local history and Wine Tradition". On the other hand the main barriers for tourists who want to be engaged in wine tourism was elements such as "cost", "accessibility", and "distance of the destination".

The results is a valuable input for policy makers and entrepreneurs in order to develop and promote a wine destination and increase wine tourist's satisfaction and Loyalty.

Abstract 46

The behaviour of the new gamer consumer when faced with the advertising placement of fashion brands in videogames.

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KEYWORDS: Fashion marketing, gamer, neuromarketing, videogames.

ABSTRACT: The research explores perceptions, purchasing decisions, sense of belonging and brand loyalty among gamers, focusing mainly on the realm of fashion marketing. Specifically, it explores the dynamics of advertising placement for fashion brands within videogames, aiming to shed light on this relatively unexplored area and potentially uncover a new profile of fashion consumers. Since the inception of advertising, its influence on mass audiences has been undeniable. However, technological advancements have resulted in advertising saturation in traditional media, prompting audiences to migrate towards streaming platforms (Ramos, 2016). Moreover, to effectively reach contemporary consumers, new advertising strategies must prioritize placement as a critical tactic (Martín, 2018). This approach circumvents saturation by seamlessly integrating brands into external audiovisual content, such as movies, fostering authenticity and narrative connection (Seoane et al., 2015).

In contrast, the emergence of videogames as a non-conventional communication medium has enabled brands to forge emotional connections with gamers through advertising placement (Lista, 2010). This strategy not only cultivates gamer loyalty by fostering positive attitudes and enhancing purchase intent but also establishes coherence and affinity between the brand and the videogame content (Martín, 2018). Moreover, academic interest in videogames as a communication medium began with Advergames and Adverworld in arcade machines (Martín, 2018).

Firstly, a meticulously designed web survey will be deployed to explore the purchasing decisions, sense of belonging, and brand loyalty among regular and non-regular gamers. This survey aims to gather insights from approximately 400 individuals spanning various age groups and genders, conducted throughout February and March 2025. Data collection methods will include social media platforms, email and participants at events. Secondly, neuromarketing techniques such as eye-tracking and facial coding will be employed to evaluate the efficacy of fashion brand advertising within videogames. Specifically, Implicit Response Tests (IRT) will gauge the effectiveness of advertising stimuli, while the Implicit Association Test (IAT) will ascertain the connections between fashion brand advertisements and videogame genres. These neuromarketing methodologies will be instrumental in unravelling the psyche of the videogame consumer. To this end, a sample of 30 individuals spanning diverse age brackets will be recruited, comprising 15 avid gamers (heavy gamers) and 15 occasional gamers (soft gamers).

Expected results embrace new insights into gamer behaviour, the impact of videogame advertising on consumer perceptions and innovative strategies for fashion brands. This study significantly contributes to unravelling the intricacies of the digital consumer landscape, providing fashion brands with valuable insights to navigate the shifting technological landscape and adapt to the imperatives of the digital economy. Furthermore, this research aims to enrich the academic discourse by delving into gamers' responses to fashion brand advertising in videogames, drawing on neuromarketing methodologies and addressing theoretical incongruities. These findings have significant practical implications that transcend academia, shaping marketing strategies in fashion and videogame industries. These practical implications can generate tangible and intangible benefits for brands. The study promises to offer valuable insights into consumer behaviour in this thriving digital age by exploring the intersection between fashion marketing and videogames.

Abstract 47

Impact of Sustainability on Tourist Satisfaction in Rural and Urban Areas in Spain From Online Reviews.

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KEYWORDS: Sustainability, sustainable Tourism, rural Tourism, user-generated content, online reviews.

ABSTRACT: This research examines the influence of sustainability on tourist satisfaction in rural and urban areas of Spain, using online reviews from TripAdvisor. The research aims to balance the needs of tourists, the industry, and the environment by promoting sustainable tourism development, which is essential for ensuring long-term living conditions for future generations. Tourism contributes significantly to economic and social progress but also poses negative impacts such as climate change, pollution, and waste generation. Therefore, the tourism sector has a responsibility towards the environments and societies where it operates. Rural and urban tourism offer distinct challenges and opportunities; rural tourism helps reduce poverty, conserve nature, and promote local culture, while urban tourism integrates into the broader economic and social landscape of cities.

The research's objective is to analyze how sustainability impacts user satisfaction in hotels and restaurants, comparing rural and urban contexts within Spain. It investigates how economic, environmental, social, and cultural dimensions of sustainability—both explicitly and implicitly mentioned in online reviews—affect overall satisfaction and ratings.

The methodology involves collecting user-generated content (UGC) from TripAdvisor using web scraping. The sample includes 265,567 hotel reviews and 132,578 restaurant reviews from the top 425 establishments in Spain, covering the period from 2012 to 2023. The data is classified into rural and urban categories according to Spanish Law 45/2007 on Sustainable Rural Development. The study employs the “BETO cased” language model to categorize the content of reviews into sustainable dimensions. Each comment is scored across environmental, cultural, social, economic, and other categories. Generalized ordered logistic regression (gologit) are used to assess the impact of these dimensions on user ratings.

The tools and techniques used include web scraping with Octoparse, the “BETO cased” language model for categorizing comments, and BERTopic for topic modeling. Statistical analyses are performed using Stata software, with regression models and topic modeling to identify central themes in the reviews.

Results indicate that cultural content in reviews positively influences hotel and restaurant ratings, while social aspects tend to lower scores. Environmental and economic content in hotel reviews generally increases the likelihood of higher scores, whereas such content in restaurant reviews does not significantly impact ratings. Longer reviews are typically associated with lower scores. A notable difference between rural and urban areas is observed in the impact of economic content on hotel ratings; rural hotel reviews with economic content tend to receive lower ratings, whereas urban hotel reviews with similar content tend to receive higher ratings. Topic modeling shows that hotel reviews often mention environmental aspects like ambiance and specific locations, while restaurant reviews highlight cultural aspects such as different culinary styles.

This research contributes to the literature on tourism, big data, and UGC by applying innovative methodologies to extract sustainable perceptions from online reviews and assess their influence on user satisfaction. The findings offer valuable insights for hotel and restaurant managers, helping them refine their sustainability communication and marketing strategies. Understanding which sustainable attributes are most valued by users in different geographic contexts can guide more effective and targeted improvement efforts.

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